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European forum of the software research community

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Cross-fertilization workshop report – v3

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Abstract:	This deliverable is the third of a set of deliverables describing the results from the organised cross-fertilization workshops that are planned in the project, in both their public and private sessions. This is the result of task T2.1.
Keyword List:	Cross-fertilization, discussion Forum, workshop
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Terms and abbreviations

AI	Artificial Intelligence
CSA	Coordination and Support Actions
DoA	Description of Action
EC	European Commission
GA	Grant Agreement to the project
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
SW	Software
SE	Software Engineering
R&D	Research and Development
ICT	Information and Communication Technologies
SWForum.eu	European Forum of the Software research community

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Executive Summary

This deliverable is an extension of the results described in D2.2 (Cross-fertilization workshop report - v2) [1], where we have reported about the hybrid WEGreen workshop, co-hosted by SWForum.eu and HUB4CLOUD, on the topic of “Engineering Green and Sustainable Software in the Computing Continuum” [2], [3], [4], which was organised under the task T2.1.

The main objective of task T2.1 is to organize and deliver three workshops involving stakeholders from academia, industry and the public sector, representing different domains and application sectors. The workshops are important events to facilitate synergy-ignition among R&D EC funded projects, as well as a dissemination opportunity.

In this deliverable D2.3 (Cross-fertilization workshop report – v3) we present the final workshops organised by SwForum.eu, on the topics of Computing in the Cloud Continuum, Open Source, and the Challenges in the Software Engineering.

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1 Introduction

SWForum.eu aims to create a self-sustainable online forum that facilitates and encourages both researchers and practitioners as well as projects in software, digital infrastructure and cybersecurity to create intersections of expertise and a multidisciplinary approach to research and innovation [4]. This forum seeks to set in place the European research roadmap and offer cross-fertilisation of competencies to all other research and innovation areas.

SWForum.eu works to enhance the visibility and competitiveness of research and innovation in the field of software technologies, digital infrastructure and cybersecurity, especially European funded Research and Innovation Action (RIA) projects. Moreover, the project aims to introduce best practices and technology transfer opportunities to cross-synergise European excellence.

SWForum.eu project runs from 1 October 2020 through 30 June 2023. It is a CSA (Coordination and Support Action) project under the Horizon2020 program: H2020-ICT-2020-1/ CSA ICT-50-2020-1 Software Technologies, with 5 partners: Conceptivity, University of Oxford, Politecnico di Milano, TecNALIA, and Trust-IT Services.

The main objective of the SWForum.eu project is to raise awareness and strengthen the competitiveness of the European Software Industry - including the underlying digital infrastructures together with the needed security mechanisms - by facilitating a sustainable European Forum for stakeholders representing scientific researchers, service providers, software developers, operators and policy-makers relevant to software technologies, digital infrastructures and cybersecurity, where assets (products, services, technologies) can be shared, lessons learned, and policies developed, and facilitating engagement in the development of a set of research and innovation roadmaps for the Future Secure Digital Continuum through an online platform.

Within this context, SWForum.eu has promoted EU cross-fertilization between the areas of software, digital infrastructures, and cybersecurity. This goal has been achieved by organizing a self-sustainable Forum (Objective 2 in the Grant Agreement) in the context of which workshops on specific cross-fertilization themes have been organized and driven toward the publication of joint papers, joint policy papers around the topics, the creation of new initiatives, and the launch of new ideas.

The aim is to create a *living Forum* that involves, on a voluntary basis, individuals (researchers, industry representatives and end-users) interested in the future of EU research and innovation actions in the context of software technologies. In order to engage and increase stakeholder participation, SWForum.eu proposes to create a Fellowship programme, which serves to maintain a fluid pool of experts from a balanced set of SWForum.eu target stakeholder groups. This group of high-profile, acknowledged experts in their respective domains create an attractive “pull” effect on potential participants in these activities and events, as well as maintain a high level of excellence in the interactions within the Forum. In general, the Forum contributes to the definition of the future European research roadmaps and stay in touch with the EC to provide inputs, highlight needs from multiple stakeholders, and the like. SWForum.eu promotes the creation of this Forum, and most importantly, it drives the definition of a self-sustaining governance strategy and business model that permits the sustainability of the organisation to survive beyond the end of the project.

Overall, SWForum.eu is considered as a:

- ❑ Unique opportunity for European software researchers to discuss topics, issues, trends, and concerns.
- ❑ Way to make our voices heard by developing recommendations to feed into policy-making decision processes.
- ❑ Professional online platform, namely for:

- Identifying topical groups
- Creating profiles
- Developing discussion threads
- Likes/ dislikes/ recommending

1.1 About this deliverable

The purpose of this deliverable is twofold: 1) to report about the organization and execution of the final SwForum.eu workshops that we have held during the second period of the project, and 2) to reflect on lessons learnt in order to derive some valuable policy recommendations for the EC.

The presented workshops were supported by the European Commission under the programme H2020 by the projects SWForum.eu (Grant Agreement n. 957044).

1.2 Document structure

This document is organized as follows:

- ▣ Section 2 presents briefly the goals, scope, organisation, and main take away from the Open-Source Workshops for Computing and Sustainability being held on 2 Dec. 2022 in collaboration with the EC.
- ▣ Section 3 gives an overview of the organisation, execution and main take away from the First FASTContinuum Workshop held on 16 April 2023 in Coimbra, Portugal.
- ▣ Section 4 describes the final workshop The Way Forward: Workshop on Future Challenges in Software Engineering held on 27 June in Milan, Italy, in terms of its goals, scope, theme, organisation, discussion, and main take away.
- ▣ Section 5 focuses on the achieved results, considerations and lessons learnt.
- ▣ Finally, Section 6 draws conclusions.

As it is stated in the Appendix A, this report is accompanied by 3 pdfs which are the graphically enhanced post workshops reports created for some of the workshops.

2 Open-Source Workshops for Computing and Sustainability

2.1 Scope and Organisation

The “**Open-Source Workshops for Computing and Sustainability**” [5] was held on 2 December 2022 at the premises of the EC. It was organised in the form of interdisciplinary sessions focused on different domains and digital transformation key enabling technologies such as Computing Continuum, Artificial Intelligence and Quantum Computing, with the objective of leveraging the power of OSS and OSH to increase the European sovereignty, digital autonomy and advance towards a sustainable ecosystem of intensive software companies and public administrations relying on open and sustainable software solutions.

The programme was designed based on topic-focused participatory workshops, with the participation of EC representatives and relevant stakeholders from the different domains conforming the open-source community, user companies and public administrations looking for sharing experience and driving the actions towards the next generation of OS-based technologies and digital services.

More specifically, the event was focused on [5]:

- ❑ Open Source for building an Open Computing Architecture from the processor to the applications
- ❑ The role of Open Source as an innovation enabler and sustainable business support
- ❑ Open-source contribution towards the European Digital Sovereignty and Digital Autonomy
- ❑ Economic impact of Open source in the industry and in the public sector

The list of the workshops held is as follows:

- ❑ OSWS1.1 - Open-Source Processors for the Cloud Continuum
- ❑ OSWS1.2 - The role of Open-Source Software in Artificial Intelligence enabled systems: Speeding the AI adoption through OSS
- ❑ OSWS1.3 - Building Sustainable Open-Source Ecosystems for an Interoperable Europe. How can we create a sustainable Open-Source ecosystem to support the new intergovernmental cooperation framework in the Interoperable Europe Act?
- ❑ OSWS1.4 - Identifying, fixing, and managing critical Open-Source software used by European Public Services
- ❑ OSWS2.1 - Open-Source Software and Cloud Services and Applications: On the way to more interoperable cloud services
- ❑ OSWS2.2 - The potential of the symbiosis of Quantum Computing and OSS: Development of quantum computing OS algorithms and software
- ❑ OSWS2.3 - Encouraging open-source business applications reuse via the creation of an EU wide Applications Catalogue for European Public Services
- ❑ OSWS2.4 - Encouraging open-source business applications reuse via the creation of an EU-wide Applications Catalogue for European Public Services
- ❑ OSWS3.1 - Open standards and industrial use for Open Source: Leveraging the sustainability of Open-Source projects and increasing competition and interoperability between different steps in value-chains
- ❑ OSWS3.2 - Towards a trustworthy and secure ecosystem of OSS: Increasing the reliability and adoption of OSS projects
- ❑ OSWS3.3 - Agreeing, measuring and encouraging organisational contribution to the Open-Source ecosystem
- ❑ OSWS3.4 - Exploring practical solutions to ensure long term sustainability of Open-Source software

The beginning of the event was organized in one opening session followed by two keynote talks. The main slots were organized in 3 workshop sessions, with four parallel workshops each.

The schedule of the workshop's sessions is on the link:

<https://www.swforum.eu/events/open-source-workshops-computing-sustainability>

2.1 The workshop execution

All the sessions were chaired by European Commission representatives or supporting initiatives invited such as the SWForum.eu or QUCATS CSAs, who along with the panellists (3 to 5 per session) managed each workshop, actively promoting the participation by the attendees invited. In the following paragraphs, the main conclusions per workshop have been summarized [5].

WS1.1- Open-Source Processors for the Cloud Continuum (Chair: Luis Carlos Busquets, CNECT-E2)

Open Source software initiatives have produced a full stack that goes all the way down to the kernel level – but below that, much or all is still closed. Open Source Instruction Set Architectures (ISAs) are becoming increasingly attractive – in particular, RISC-V is gaining much momentum. Integrating Open Source ISAs below the kernel level will make it possible to deploy European technology (e.g., emerging from the European Processor Initiative) in its infrastructures and become digitally autonomous. Only RISC-V currently fulfils that requirement, and for that reason, is a promising ISA for Europe to adopt. Gaps must still be filled around the RISC-V architecture, including missing memory interfaces, communications IP such as PCI Express, and a European standard socket definition. There are special requirements also on cloud server processors (such as support for virtual machines). The concept of a “chiplets market” is a promising way forward to build a thriving European RISC-V ecosystem, exploiting the capabilities of Europe’s innovative but resource-strapped SMEs to combine Open Source with targeted products in a “mix and match” chiplets context. Although similar in concept, Open Source software and hardware have very different costs of production, and the provision of funding to Open Source hardware developers (rather than companies) will be even more critical to the emergence of a thriving Open Source hardware ecosystem in Europe.

WS1.2-The role of OSS in Artificial Intelligence enabled systems: Speeding the AI adoption through OSS (Chair: Miguel Esteras /SWForum.eu)

AI has acquired a strategic stature within the vision of the European Commission, and a multi-pronged set of objectives is evolving based upon not only technological considerations but also policy-oriented considerations such as ethical issues in AI. OS has the potential to make significant contributions to each of these objectives. Technologically, much of current AI research, and especially the sub-discipline of Machine Learning (ML), makes use of large, mature open-source components (TensorFlow, etc.). ML also makes heavy use of large datasets for training of the neural networks, and here the principles of Open Data can promote the widespread availability of datasets in all sectors of ML application, ranging from language processing to machine vision. The use of OS software and hardware to make available open platforms / testbeds / facilities for testing AI based applications is also an important challenge to explore. Availability of data is going to be a challenge (also with 5G) and therefore data space design principles are needed as well as a common OS infrastructure in Europe for data spaces, i.e., Gaia-X.

WS1.3- Building Sustainable Open-Source Ecosystems for an Interoperable Europe. How can we create a sustainable Open -Source ecosystem to support the new intergovernmental cooperation framework in the Interoperable Europe Act? (Chair: Leontina Sandu / DIGIT D2), and Monika Sowinska / DIGIT)

This workshop focused on the Interoperable Europe Act that reinforce European cooperation on interoperability. The Act focuses on collaboration between the Member States and the European Commission. In particular, Open-Source communities, both in the public and private sector are impacted by the Act.

The Act's ambitions were discussed in view of the recommendations of the Expert group. In particular:

- ❏ Recommendation n°9: Support exchange of best practices amongst Member States (e.g., Open Source, GovTech, pilots, etc.)
- ❏ Recommendation n°23: Better support Open-Source Software
- ❏ Recommendation n°24: Provide a catalogue of Open-Source solutions for the public sector.

WS1.4- Identifying, fixing and managing critical Open-Source software used by European Public Services (Chair: Miguel Diez Blanco / DIGIT and Saranjit Arora / EC OSPO)

With thousands of Open Source software, tools and libraries in use, it is impossible to accurately know the health (long-term upkeep, evolution and maintenance) of each component. Any failure could have severe consequences for the parent application e.g., the recent [Log4J](#) vulnerability. Any important but vulnerable software can be considered as *critical software*. The European Commission's FOSSEPS project recently completed [a study](#) to identify critical software in use at European Public Services. There is a debate about how we prevent software from becoming critical, and how to fix the criticality. Perhaps even more important is how to identify such software in the first place, even if we had a Software Bill Of Materials (SBOM).

During this session attendees have better understood the Critical Software and solutions to better identify and fix critical Open Source software within their organisations. Ideas such as the US Whitehouse's [executive order](#) to use Software Bill Of Materials (SBOM) and OSS scanning tools were also discussed.

WS2.1 – Open-Source Software and Cloud Services and Applications: On the way to more interoperable cloud services (Chair: Leire Orue-Echevarria / EC CONNECT)

The goal of this session is to analyse, discuss and understand how cloud continuum – based applications and services can benefit from, and contribute to Open Source software in order to promote interoperability and portability, seeking to reduce vendor lock-in and cover the whole cloud stack while at the same time ensuring trustworthiness and security. Issues such as the challenges faced to distribute trustworthy and interoperable cloud and edge services as Open Source software, finding the appropriate business models, monetization and licenses in the case of cloud services and applications, and how to engage the community and achieve a success governance model were discussed.

WS2.2 – The potential of the symbiosis of Quantum Computing and OSS: Development of quantum computing OS algorithms and software (Chair: Fanny Bouton / OVHCloud)

Due to its incipient stage of development, Quantum Computing is hybrid by nature. It offers a specialized form of computing power which needs to co-exist with classical architectures in the form of hybrid computing approaches. Therefore, interoperability and reusability are key aspects to take into consideration. A hybrid quantum stack will require management and orchestration to ensure that programs, experiments, processes, and technologies run smoothly and are interoperable. In this context, OS can and should play a relevant role in the future of the Quantum ecosystem, especially from the hardware and software perspectives. In this context, at European level specialization in certain domains (such as chemistry or biology) is seen as the correct strategy to follow in order to compete with other big players and take advantage of the momentum that the frameworks of these big players are creating around the software developer community. The need for the creation of a network serving a European Quantum

community could also leverage on existing OS communities to foster cooperation, collaboration and networking between the main European players.

WS2.3 – Encouraging open-source business applications reuse via the creation of an EU wide Applications Catalogue for European Public Services (Chair: Evangelos Tsavalopoulos / DIGIT B3.002 and Saranjit Arora / EC OSPO)

This workshop focused on how the PAs across Europe have built a huge number of business applications over the years using OSS tools, as well as how the same applications were rebuilt within each country and across the EU. An important discussion was about the emerging national OS application catalogues and the need for a Europe-wide one. Possible solution of trying to reuse applications systems that already exist was discussed. Also, the DIGIT unit at the EC has been collaborating with the EU Parliament to build such a European catalogue, which is expected to be ready in June 2023. However, this product is not standalone – it is necessary to integrate information from existing catalogues.

WS2.4 – Encouraging open-source business applications reuse via the creation of an EU wide Applications Catalogue for European Public Services (Chair: Gijs Hillenius /DIGIT and Miguel Diez Blanco / DIGIT)

This session focused on a debate about the Cooperation – how much happens today, regionally, nationally or across EU – what the barriers are, how it can be improved. Do we have the right cooperation channels? What can be shared - experiences, expertise, funds, code, applications? Can public administrations collectively fund developments, security bug bounties? Who is applying Open Source internally, i.e., inner sourcing, has it helped?

The panellists strongly feel that it is irresponsible for the public administration to only spend money on themselves and not collaborate with others. This can also be accelerated by being more open to trying out solutions built elsewhere in Europe and not just in their own countries. It was also suggested to have a fully funded Open Source foundation that can promote the collaboration on projects. However, creating such an organization is a long and expensive project. Instead, having an educational Erasmus program for Open Source developers and residents can help people understand that sharing something can help them gain instead of lose something. It is a win-win for everyone.

WS3.1 – Open standards and industrial use for Open Source: Leveraging the sustainability of Open-Source projects and increasing competition and interoperability between different steps in value-chains (Chair: John Favaro / SWForum.eu)

Company policies towards open source embrace the use of and contribution to software that is crucial for its products. Raising awareness of OS possibilities has been identified as an effective policy for increasing economic growth. OS assets facilitate making an efficient use of resources and increase industrial competitiveness. Together with standards they are embedded in nearly all electronic devices we use in our daily live. Computers, TVs, electrical appliances, phones, cars are using millions of lines of code from projects initially started by hundreds of volunteer developers and shared with all. Also, many OS projects implement open standards.

However, there are different expectations about what open standards are (i.e., more examples of open-source implementations of open standards) and can do and a unified definition at European level is needed. Small organizations need help to deal with the regulations, and the EC could help them in this process. Also, the adoption of open-source software while actively addressing the associated need for adopting open standards should be led through EC mandates. Software developers should be invited together with other bigger players to set up and participate in the discussion tables promoting “bottom up” approaches for the open standards creation processes (following the “de facto” standards strategy) focusing on implementing first; seeing what works; and shaping standards from the proven implementation.

WS3.2 – Towards a trustworthy and secure ecosystem of OSS: Increasing the reliability and adoption of OSS projects (Chair: James Galand-Jones / EC-Connect)

From the surveys conducted by the EC as part of the study *“The impact of Open-Source Software and Hardware on technological independence, competitiveness and innovation in the EU economy”* cybersecurity and trustworthiness of OSS and OSH was of significant importance. A particular concern identified is related to the ability of chips or software components to incorporate backdoors or malware embedded by a bad actor in the supply chain. The ability to develop and maintain a root of trust, through the supply chain is facilitated by open hardware and software. This impact will increase over time.

The detection of cybersecurity attacks needs to be addressed from a holistic point of view with the incorporation of best practices, new processes, and tools to prevent attacks. The upcoming CRA legislation has the objective of increasing the cyber resilience of software and hardware artifacts, manufactured, developed, and operated in Europe, including commercial Open-Source projects. Of course, the CRA needs to consider the special nature of open source as a frictionless collaboration, and to preserve the innovative character of European actors in the application of the CRA, reflecting the complexity of the OS world.

WS3.3 – Agreeing, measuring and encouraging organisational contribution to the Open-Source ecosystem (Chair: Saranjit Arora / EC OSPO and Miguel Diez Blanco / DIGIT B3.002)

This workshop focused on OS business applications reuse via the creation of an EU wide applications catalogue for European public services. Some initiatives in the ecosystem at the Ministry of Digital Affairs in France were presented as good practices.

Another initiative which was pointed out is the [Blue Hats](#), a symbol used in public administrations for people interested in and learning about OS. The initiative has proven to be quite useful. Another initiative mentioned was to incentivise the executives to be conscious about the critical software they use. So, the key issues were discussed by the panellists in the workshop.

WS3.4 – Exploring practical solutions to ensure long term sustainability of Open-Source software (Chair: Chrysanthi Giortsou / DY and Gijs Hillenius / DIGIT)

This session explores practical methods of supporting key groups responsible for sustainability of software. Methods include financial compensation and provision of work. It also explores why we do not already support these groups, what the barriers are and how we can overcome those. It also elicits ideas of how a [European Funding Mechanism](#) can be realised.

A large number of possible solutions around increased diversity and culture built around SMEs and individuals in the Open Source community as well as some innovative ideas to involve people and their views into the funding landscape. All these solutions would be further discussed in the Commission and acted upon in the near future.

2.2 Main takeaways

The main takeaways from the discussion could be summarised in the following challenges:

- ❑ The EC finds it important to bring the constituency together to discuss relevant topics for Europe such as Open Source and will continue to foster discussion, cross-fertilization and collaboration between all stakeholders.
- ❑ The EC is committed to put into action the conclusions from the discussions, especially through investment opportunities such as the Horizon Europe Work programme and the upcoming calls including research topics where OS can play a significant role (i.e.,

research topics on OS for Cloud and Edge to support European autonomy, research topics in the fundamentals of Software Engineering, and CSA-based instruments to promote visibility of OS outcomes from the projects). The OS community can also have a relevant role in the industrial calls where skilled OS professionals can propose OS solutions.

- The EC is also promoting and fostering the adoption of OS based solutions that support the European Digital Transformation, especially in the context of:
- Development of the Data Economy, linked to the development of Artificial Intelligence networks under European values and supported by fair rules such as the Data Act, which will guarantee users control over their data, and open standards, which will avoid vendor lock-in while fostering data interoperability and enabling seamless change of provider.
 - The EC is aware of the enormous economic potential of adopting OS solutions for the digital transformation of European society and industry. With the “lead by example” approach, the EC is boosting the usage and adoption of OS solutions in local and national public administrations.
 - The EC is also working on a rulebook to be used as guidance, both from the PA perspective and user perspective, for the adoption of OS solutions.

3 The First FASTContinuum Workshop¹

Nowadays, cloud computing is widely used by industry with an estimate of the worldwide cloud market of about 940 USD billion with a compound annual growth rate of about 16%. Cloud computing provides, among others, the capacity to run the backend of web applications, or train artificial intelligence applications, or run big data analytics. However, the accelerated migration towards mobile computing and the Internet of Things, where a huge amount of data is generated by widespread end-devices, is determining the rise of the computing continuum paradigm, where resources are distributed among devices with highly heterogeneous capacities. This promises reduced latency and higher throughput thanks to local processing. However, there are still many open challenges concerning the fast development, testing, and operation of computing continuum software, especially when we must provide specific performance guarantees in the end-to-end application execution. Indeed, computing continua are inherently fragmented, IoT/edge devices being highly heterogeneous providing different computing capabilities but also introducing proprietary development, deployment, and operation frameworks. In this context, dominating the complexity of multiple coexisting frameworks, as well as managing component placement and resource allocation, become crucial to orchestrate at best the continuum of resources.

The FastContinuum workshop has been co-organized by partners from the projects SwForum, AI-Sprint, and PIACERE and has been held as a workshop of the 14th ACM/SPEC International Conference on Performance Engineering (ICPE 2023). The General Chairs have been Elisabetta Di Nitto and Danilo Ardagna from Politecnico di Milano. The Program Chairs have been Lorenzo Blasi from Hewlett-Packard Enterprise and Francesc Lordan from Barcelona Supercomputing Center.

3.1 Goal, Scope and Theme

The goal of the workshop has been to foster discussion and collaboration among researchers from cloud/edge/fog computing and performance analysis communities, to share the relevant topics and results of the current approaches proposed by industry and academia.

¹ <https://sites.google.com/view/fastcontinuum-2023/home>

FastContinuum solicited full papers as well as demo and short papers including reports about research activities not mature enough for a full paper as well as new ideas and vision papers.

The topics of interest included but were not limited to:

- ▣ Modeling and evaluation of computing continuum applications performance
- ▣ Cloud, edge, grid, and fog as continuum components
- ▣ Computing continuum benchmarking
- ▣ Autonomous, resilient and adaptive systems, and applications
- ▣ Application to resource mapping optimization, tasks scheduling
- ▣ Microservices in the computing continuum, Function as a Service systems
- ▣ Data-intensive and stream processing systems and applications
- ▣ Machine learning and artificial intelligence applications
- ▣ Cyber-physical systems, IoT, industrial internet
- ▣ Infrastructure as a Service and Infrastructure as Code, automation in the computing continuum
- ▣ Modeling and verification of application deployment plans
- ▣ DevSecOps for computing continuum applications
- ▣ Computing continuum monitoring
- ▣ Sandbox environments for simulation/emulation of continuum resources

3.2 Organisation and Format

The workshop's Organizing Committee was constituted by the following members:

- ▣ General co-chairs: Elisabetta Di Nitto and Danilo Ardagna (Politecnico di Milano)
- ▣ Program co-chairs: Lorenzo Blasi (Hewlett-Packard Enterprise) and Francesc Lordan (Barcelona Supercomputing Center)
- ▣ Web chair: Hamta Sedghani (Politecnico di Milano)
- ▣ Publicity chair: Galia Novakova Nedeltcheva (Politecnico di Milano)

The important dates for the participants were as follows:

- ▣ Workshop paper submissions: January 22, 2023. Extended to January 29, 2023
- ▣ Notification of acceptance: February 13, 2023
- ▣ Camera-ready copies: February 20, 2023
- ▣ Workshop date: April 15 or 16, 2023 TBC

Authors were invited to submit original, unpublished papers that are not being considered in another forum. We solicited full papers (max. 8 pages) as well as short and demo papers (max. 5 pages). Short papers are the one including reports about research activities not mature enough for a full paper as well as new ideas and vision papers. All submissions were conformed to the standard ACM template for conference proceedings: <https://www.acm.org/publications/proceedings-template>. More specifically, the double-column formats had to be used for all paper submissions. Each paper submission was reviewed by at least three members of the program committee. Papers were submitted via EasyChair: <https://easychair.org/my/conference?conf=icpe2023>, FastContinuum 2023 workshop track. Papers were published by ACM in the ICPE2023 Companion Proceedings volume. At least one author of each accepted paper was required to attend the workshop and present the paper.

Proceedings:

ICPE: [dl.acm.org/doi/proceedings/10.1145/3578244](https://doi.org/10.1145/3578244)

ICPE Companion: [dl.acm.org/doi/proceedings/10.1145/3578245](https://doi.org/10.1145/3578245)

3.3 Workshop execution

The First FASTContinuum workshop took place on 16 April 2023 at Coimbra, Portugal (www.icpe2023.spec.org/venue/) in conjunction with the International Conference on Performance Measurement (ICPE 2023, <https://sites.google.com/view/fastcontinuum-2023/home>). Also, this SwForum.eu workshop was co-organised together with [AI-SPRINT](#) and [PIACERE](#) projects.

The final program included four full papers and three short ones covering some of the most interesting areas of computing continua, from FaaS development and acceleration to the management of heterogeneous datasets to the development of Infrastructure as Code and the automation of deployment through the computing continuum. DevSecOps has been also brought to the attendees' attention as one of the crucial ingredients for proper management of the continuum.

The workshop was organised in four sessions and a panel during one-day. One of the sessions accommodated the accepted full papers, while in another one the accepted short papers were presented. The number of participants was around 40. The list of all accepted papers at the First FastContinuum workshop is presented below.

The full program with all the presentations is available on: https://sites.google.com/view/fastcontinuum-2023/program_1

Accepted Papers

List of full papers:

- ❏ Diana María Naranjo Delgado, Manuel Contreras, Germán Moltó, Sebastián Risco, Ignacio Blanquer, Javier Prades and Federico Silla. *On the Acceleration of FaaS using Remote GPU Virtualization.*
- ❏ George Kousiouris, Szymon Ambroziak, Blazej Zarzycki, Domenico Costantino, Stylianos Tsarsitalidis, Vasileios Katevas, Alessandro Mamelli and Teta Stamati. *A Pattern-based Function and Workflow Visual Environment for FaaS Development across the Continuum.*
- ❏ Alberto Archetti, Eugenio Lomurno, Francesco Lattari, André Martin and Matteo Matteucci. *Heterogeneous Datasets for Federated Survival Analysis Simulation.*
- ❏ Matthijs Jansen, Linus Wagner, Animesh Trivedi and Alexandru Iosup. *Continuum: Automate Infrastructure Deployment and Benchmarking in the Compute Continuum.*

List of short papers:

- ❏ Galia Novakova Nedeltcheva, Bin Xiang, Laureniu Niculut and Debora Benedetto. *Challenges Towards Modeling and Generating Infrastructure-as-Code.*
- ❏ Josu Diaz-de-Arcaya, Eneko Osaba, Gorka Benguria, Iñaki Etxaniz, Jesus L. Lobo, Juncal Alonso, Ana I. Torre-Bastida and Aitor Almeida. *IEM: A Unified Lifecycle Orchestrator for Multilingual IaC Deployments.*
- ❏ Matija Cankar, Nenad Petrović, Joao Pita Costa, Aleš Černivec, Jan Antič, Tomaž Martinčič and Dejan Štepec. *Security in DevSecOps: Applying tools and machine learning to verifications and monitoring steps.*

3.4 Keynote speaker and presentations

The workshop keynote, given by Samuel Kounev (University of Würzburg), has been focused on the area of serverless computing properly positioning the multiple aspects and approaches developed in this area and highlighting the main challenges related to the performance of these approaches. Such keynote has been held in collaboration with the eleventh International Workshop on Load Testing and Benchmarking of Software Systems (LTB 2023).

The title of his talk was “Serverless Computing Revisited: Evolution, State-of-the-Art, and Performance Challenges”. The following paragraphs below presents summary of the talk.

Market analysts are agreed that serverless computing has strong market potential, with projected compound annual growth rates varying between 21% and 28% through 2028 and a projected market value of \$36.8 billion by that time. Although serverless computing has gained significant attention in industry and academia over the past years, there is still no consensus about its unique distinguishing characteristics and precise understanding of how these characteristics differ from classical cloud computing. For example, there is no wide agreement on whether serverless is solely a set of requirements from the cloud user’s perspective or it should also mandate specific implementation choices on the provider side, such as implementing an autoscaling mechanism to achieve elasticity. Similarly, there is no agreement on whether serverless is just the operational part, or it should also include specific programming models, interfaces, or calling protocols.

His talk tried to dispel this confusion by evaluating the essential conceptual characteristics of serverless computing as a paradigm, while putting the various terms around it into perspective. It was examined how the term serverless computing, and related terms, are used today. The historical evolution leading to serverless computing was explained, starting with mainframe virtualization in the 1960 through to Grid and cloud computing all the way up to today. A review of existing cloud computing service models was made, including IaaS, PaaS, SaaS, CaaS, FaaS, and BaaS, discussing how they relate to the serverless paradigm. In the second part of talk, the focus was on performance challenges in serverless computing both from the user's perspective (finding the optimal size of serverless functions) as well as from the provider's perspective (ensuring predictable and fast container start times coupled with fine-granular and accurate elastic scaling mechanisms).

Before the Keynote speech there were two sessions on the Function as a Service and DevSecOps:

Session 1 Function as a Service, chaired by Danilo Ardagna (Politecnico di Milano). This session has included the following two presentations:

- ❏ *On the Acceleration of FaaS using Remote GPU Virtualization* - Diana María Naranjo Delgado, Manuel Contreras, Germán Moltó, Sebastián Risco, Ignacio Blanquer, Javier Prades and Federico Silla.
- ❏ *A Pattern-based Function and Workflow Visual Environment for FaaS Development across the Continuum* - George Kousiouris, Szymon Ambroziak, Blazej Zarzycki, Domenico Costantino, Stylianos Tsarsitalidis, Vasileios Katevas, Alessandro Mamelli and Teta Stamati.

Session 2 DevSecOps, chaired by Francesc Lordan (Barcelona Supercomputer Center) and Danilo Ardagna (PoliMi). This session has included the following presentation.

- ❏ *Security in DevSecOps: Applying tools and machine learning to verifications and monitoring step* - Matija Cankar, Nenad Petrović, Joao Pita Costa, Aleš Černivec, Jan Antič, Tomaž Martinčič and Dejan Štepec.

After the keynote speech, there were another two sessions on Infrastructure as Code and on Machine Learning.

Session 3: Infrastructure as Code chaired by Elisabetta di Nitto (Politecnico di Milano). This session has included the following three presentations.

- ❏ *Continuum: Automate Infrastructure Deployment and Benchmarking in the Compute Continuum* - Matthijs Jansen, Linus Wagner, Animesh Trivedi and Alexandru Iosup.

- ❏ *Challenges Towards Modelling and Generating Infrastructure-as-Code* - Galia Novakova Nedeltcheva, Bin Xiang, Laureniu Niculut and Debora Benedetto.
- ❏ *IEM: A Unified Lifecycle Orchestrator for Multilingual IaC Deployments* - Josu Diaz-de-Arcaya, Eneko Osaba, Gorka Benguria, Iñaki Etxaniz, Jesus L. Lobo, Juncal Alonso, Ana I. Torre-Bastida and Aitor Almeida.

Session 4: Machine learning, chaired by Francesc Lordan (Barcelona Supercomputer Center). This session has included one presentation.

- ❏ *Heterogeneous Datasets for Federated Survival Analysis Simulation* - Alberto Archetti, Eugenio Lomurno, Francesco Lattari, André Martin and Matteo Matteucci.

After the four sessions there was a **Panel** on the “*Computing in the Cloud Continuum: Technological challenges, killer applications and future trends*”. The panelists have been Tania Lorigo Botran (Roblox, USA), Samuel Kounev, Matteo Matteucci (Politecnico di Milano), and Radu Prodan (University of Klagenfurt, Austria). The panel has been moderated by John Favaro from Trust-It.

The program has been concluded by a panel discussion on the current trends and evolution of cloud and computing continuum systems. With the objective of expanding the workshop discussion to a larger community, this session has been organized jointly with the sixth Workshop on Hot Topics in Cloud Computing Performance (*HotCloudPerf 2023*²).

3.5 Main takeaways

The panel produced a number of insights. One such insight was that the domains of interest in the continuum are currently so heterogeneous, ranging from AI-enabled robotics, vision, signal processing, to many more (including especially demanding low latency applications) that this heterogeneity will be one of the primary challenges going forward in serving the continuum. Because of this, we will almost certainly see domain-specific solutions rather than a single, all-embracing architecture of the continuum.

In this regard, the panelists observed that the continuum is currently wildly imbalanced, with massive cloud providers and powerful 5G facilities awkwardly co-existing with resource-scarce IoT devices, a situation of severe “impedance mismatch” in dire need of addressing before significant progress can be made.

Finally, the panel observed that the continuum will involve many societal challenges, such as helping to fight climate change, and contributing to the strengthening of the social media phenomenon through new applications such as the metaverse. Because of this, both panelists and audience came away with a new appreciation for the continuum, not only as a powerful paradigm presenting formidable but exciting technical challenges, but also as a new societal force – one that is likely to have broad impact in all of our lives – presenting its own set of ethical and social challenges for all of us to consider.

² <https://hotcloudperf.spec.org/>

4 Way Forward Workshop: Future Challenges in Software Engineering

4.1 Goal, Scope and Themes

The SWForum.eu *Way Forward Workshop on Future Challenges in Software Engineering*³ was a highly interactive workshop (in-presence) that took place on 27 June 2023 at Politecnico di Milano, in the Dipartimento di Elettronica, Informazione e Bioingegneria (DEIB). Registration was free of charge and opened until 15 June 2023.

Organising Committee (see Section 4.2) was looking for contributions related to the following topics: Software Engineering and AI, Software Engineering for Quantum Computing, Security in the Computing Continuum and Sustainable Software Engineering. The deadline for submission of contribution was 22 May 2022.

The SWForum project aims to create a self-sustainable online forum that facilitates and encourages both researchers and practitioners as well as projects in software, digital infrastructure and cybersecurity to create intersections of expertise and a multidisciplinary approach to research and innovation.

Even though the project is at the end of its funding period, it would like to continue nurturing the discussion in the community. The workshop, as in-presence one, aims at grouping together researchers and practitioners interested in discussing and creating new ideas and initiatives around the following crucial areas that were organised in four separate sessions:

- ▣ Software Engineering and AI
- ▣ Software Engineering for Quantum Computing
- ▣ Security in the Computing Quantum
- ▣ Sustainable Software Engineering

4.2 Organisation and format

The Organising Committee of the workshop was constituted by the following members:

- ▣ Juncal Alonso - TECNALIA, Spain
- ▣ Elisabetta Di Nitto, Politecnico di Milano, Italy
- ▣ John Favaro, Trust-IT, Italy
- ▣ Mark Miller, Conceptivity, Switzerland
- ▣ Vlado Stankovski, University of Ljubljana, Slovenia
- ▣ David Wallom, University of Oxford, UK

The workshop took place in presence, in order to be highly interactive and focused on open discussions in the areas listed in Section 4.2, guided by inspiring talks.

A summary of the discussion and of the new ideas emerging from it will be reported further on in more detail in a paper jointly prepared by the workshop participants and submitted to an international magazine.

The call for talks was open and anyone could propose his/ her talk by filling in the form available here: <https://forms.office.com/e/hbYayPRvVb>. Talk proposals were evaluated by the organising committee on the basis of their novelty, importance in the software engineering context, and potential impact. The accepted talks were the basis for the discussion at the workshop.

The workshop was organised in four sessions:

- ▣ Security in the Computing Continuum

³ <https://www.swforum.eu/events/swforumeu-way-forward-workshop-future-challenges-software-engineering>

- ▣ Software Engineering and AI
- ▣ Software Engineering for Quantum Computing
- ▣ Sustainable Software Engineering

The link to the agenda is here:

<https://swforum.eu/agenda-swforumeu-way-forward-workshop-future-challenges-software-engineering>

Following is a summary from the sessions' discussions.

4.3 The workshop execution

The day kicked off with a keynote address delivered by Juncal Alonso, R&D project manager and senior researcher at Tecnia and SWForum.eu project coordinator. The keynote highlighted the transformative impact of emerging technologies such as artificial intelligence, quantum computing, cybersecurity, and the cloud computing continuum on the field of software engineering.

The workshop sessions' discussions brought together a diverse array of professionals who shared their expertise on specific challenges faced by software engineers. Topics included:

- ▣ **Security in the Computing Continuum.** The session was chaired by **Mark Miller**, CEO of CONCEPTIVITY and one of the board members of the European Cybersecurity Organisation (ECISO), and featured talks and discussions from three cybersecurity experts, namely Martin Higgins (a researcher at the University of Oxford and one of the SWForum.eu fellows), Valentina Casola (associate professor at the University of Napoli Federico II), and Francesco Morano (a Cyber Security Team Researcher at CEFRIEL) on cyber-physical systems, security-by-design methodologies and security metrics and usage of artificial intelligence (AI) to automate human-related cyberattacks.
- ▣ **Software Engineering in AI.** **John Favaro**, a Senior Research Analyst at Trust-IT Services, chaired a session featuring six talks which combined best practices in software engineering with the unique challenges and considerations of developing AI systems. Experts such as Nuria Quintano Fernandez, Luciano Baresi, Michele Ciavotta, Luigi Lavazza, Marina Giordanino, and Francesco Lattari shared insights on topics like ethics, software engineering for ML, MLOps, binary classifiers, IoT/cloud operating systems, and accelerating AI application development.
- ▣ **The Software Engineering for Quantum Computing** session, chaired by **Elisabetta Di Nitto**, a professor at Politecnico di Milano, featured four talks on various aspects of quantum computing. Dario di Nucci discussed its adoption, Vlado Stankovski highlighted the role of formal probabilistic models, Eneko Osaba focused on quantum optimisation, and Paolo Cremonesi explored quantum annealing. These talks provided insights into the quantum frontier in software engineering and its potential applications.
- ▣ **The Sustainable Software Engineering** session, chaired by **David Wallom**, a professor at the University of Oxford. This session featured Radu Prodan, a professor at the University of Klagenfurt, who provided insights into extreme and sustainable graph processing, addressing urgent societal challenges in Europe. The session aimed to inspire innovative approaches and promote policies supporting software sustainability.

Below is following a summary of each presentation [6].

Session 1: Security in the Computing Continuum

Martin Higgins - University of Oxford: Cyber-Physical Systems: Attack and Defense

The objective of this talk has been to inform the audience on the risks associated in cyber-physical systems. Cyber-Physical systems are systems where computing networks interact directly with the real world. A good example being the power system wherein distribution, transmission and physical assets interact with software, computing & IT through the SCADA network. Of particular interest is deception attacks whereby an attack vector is hidden. These attacks are gaining prominence and can feature in a number of cyber-physical systems including power systems, water networks, self-driving vehicles and industrial control systems. The talk has pointed to the attacks like Stuxnet that caused significant damage to cyber-physical systems in the past.

Valentina Casola - University of Napoli Federico II: Security-by-Design methodologies and security metrics

The presentation focused on a novel Security-by-Design methodology and security metrics based on Security Service Level Agreements (SLAs), which can be integrated within modern development processes that is able to support the risk management life-cycle in an almost-completely automated way.

Francesco Morano – CEFRIEL: Usage of AI to automate human-related cyber-attacks

This talk has presented a Proof of Concept (PoC) for a semi-automatic phishing attack that uses Artificial Intelligence (AI) and discussed the usage of AIs to automate human-related cyber-attacks. The potential of AI in a full OpSec attack stack, simulating an all-out attack from a cyber criminal's perspective has been explored. Using AI tools, it is possible to implement a complete attack chain that includes collecting victims' data through OSINT, generating the phishing email body using GPT-2, and creating a graphic that mimics the actual organization's brand identity using other models. This study has helped penetration testers and red teams build targeted phishing simulations more rapidly and provides a methodological approach to social engineering attacks. It was also discussed the effectiveness of tools like ChatGPT in the current era of automated phishing using generative AIs. By approaching the problem from a cyber criminal's point of view, it is aimed to understand the feasibility of such an attack tactic and prepare countermeasures.

Session 2: Software Engineering and AI

Nuria Quintano Fernández – TECNALIA: Evaluating and validating hybrid AI algorithms and asserting their adherence to an ethical and legal overarching approach to trustworthiness

The presentation has focused on the analysis and development of tool-chains and metrics for explaining, evaluating and validating hybrid AI algorithms and asserting their adherence to an ethical and legal overarching approach to trustworthiness. This has been exemplified using real-world industrial use cases in the Robotics domain (collaboration between human and robots for logistics activities) and Space domain (failure detection for satellites) to promote the widespread adoption of hybrid AI in industrial settings.

The overarching ethical and legal approach is based on Value Sensitive Design (VSD) methodology: the end users and the technology developers are working together from the beginning of the engineering cycle to understand and define the ethical and trustworthiness characteristics. In order for the engineering team and other relevant stakeholders to understand

whether those characteristics will be present as expected/required when the system is operating, they need to quantify their current and future presence.

Furthermore, the presentation touched upon what matters regarding expected/required ethical and trustworthiness performance values, based on the market context as well as on the AI system expected use and expected confidence and model understandability.

 Luciano Baresi – Politecnico di Milano: Software Engineering for ML, some first experiences

This presentation discussed some first attempts at healing machine learning models, at improving the deployment and operation of federated learning systems and at provisioning heterogeneous resources to ease and optimise the training and inference phases of machine learning-based systems. The final goal has been to try to identify some recurring problems and some open issues for a plausible research agenda.

In particular, the presentation has touched upon the following topics:

- AI-based system properties and approaches
- Main challenges faced in the development of AI/ ML systems
- Distributed control of containers
- Federated (Machine) learning as a self-adaptive system

 Michele Ciavotta – University of Milano – Bicocca: MLOps the hard way: a journey on integrating AI and software engineering

Machine learning (ML) projects are challenging to automate and operationalize, especially when they involve collaboration between software engineers and data scientists. The speaker has shared his personal experience of working on a complex ML project that required integrating AI and software engineering principles and tools. Discussed were the main challenges and lessons learned from applying MLOps practices to manage the ML life cycle from experimentation to production.

 Luigi Lavazza - Università degli Studi dell'Insubria: AI techniques (mainly Machine Learning and Neural Networks) support the construction of prediction models

Binary classifiers (BC) are widely used in SE, for instance, to predict interesting characteristics of code modules (classes, methods, functions, etc.), as well as, in other fields related to SW constructions, e.g., for evaluating the vulnerability of code.

For both researchers and practitioners, a problem with BC is the evaluation of BCs' accuracy. Accuracy indexes have specificities (and sometimes flaws) that were largely ignored. Unfortunately, using accuracy indexes without considering their characteristics could lead to incorrect conclusions concerning the actual accuracy of BCs, with possibly serious consequences.

This talk has presented the most widely used accuracy indexes and their characteristics. Also, the consequences of the unaware usage of Accuracy Indexes were examined. Ultimately, some recommendations on how to approach BC evaluation were provided, also with reference to the consequent costs.

 Marina Giordanino – Stellantis: On the evaluation of binary classifiers for Software Engineering by Development of a IoT2cloud Operating System (ICOS)

This presentation has focused on the ICOS project aiming at covering the set of challenges that come up when addressing this continuum paradigm by proposing an approach embedding a well-defined set of functionalities, ending up in the definition of an IoT2cloud Operating System

(ICOS). Indeed, the main objective of the project ICOS was to design, develop, and validate a meta-operating system for a continuum by addressing the challenges of: i) device volatility and heterogeneity, continuum infrastructure virtualisation, and diverse network connectivity; ii) optimized and scalable service execution and performance, as well as resource consumptions, including power consumption; iii) guaranteed trust, security, and privacy; and iv) reduction of integration costs and effective mitigation of cloud provider lock-in effects, in a data-driven system built upon the principles of openness, adaptability, data sharing, and a future edge market scenario for services and data.

 Francesco Latteri – Politecnico di Milano: AI-SPRINT: Design and Runtime Framework for accelerating the development of AI Applications in the Computing Continuum

This presentation has focused on the AI-SPRINT “Artificial intelligence in Secure PRiVacy-preserving computing coNTinuum” project and its aim to develop a framework composed of design and runtime management tools to seamlessly design, partition and operate Artificial Intelligence (AI) applications among the current plethora of cloud-based solutions and AI-based sensor devices (i.e., devices with intelligence and data processing capabilities), providing resource efficiency, performance, data privacy, and security guarantees.

AI-SPRINT design workflow involves key tools for the automatic generation of Docker images for the containerized execution of application components (TOSCARIZER), for the automatic profiling of application performance (OSCAR-P), and for the automated design space exploration to provide the optimal production deployments (SPACE4AI-D). Design tools, further enriched with tools for neural architecture search (NAS), federated learning, and privacy preserving model execution, make AI-SPRINT an advanced framework that fills known technology gaps, by providing solutions to efficiently develop and deploy AI enterprise applications across the computing continuum.

Session 3: Software Engineering for Quantum Computing

 Dario Di Nucci – University of Salerno: The Quantum Frontier of Software Engineering and its Adoption

Quantum computing is no longer only a scientific interest but is rapidly becoming an industrially available technology that can potentially overcome the limits of classical computation.

This talk has presented the challenges developers experience when dealing with quantum technology and how academia is trying to solve them.

On the one hand, it has been showcased a taxonomy of the purposes for which quantum technologies are used and the results of our interviews to elicit developers' opinions on the current adoption and challenges of quantum programming.

On the other hand, it was reported on the results of a systematic mapping study we conducted to understand the current state of quantum software engineering research, aiming to identify the most investigated topics, the main reported results, and the most studied quantum computing tools and frameworks.

 Vlado Stankovski -University of Ljubljana: The Role of Formal Probabilistic Models in Quantum Computing

In many potential applications of quantum computing, there is the promise of being able to solve complex problems that cannot be efficiently tackled by existing supercomputers. This talk has explored the possibility of information management in quantum computing via formal probabilistic models. The idea behind is to enable two new concepts in quantum computing: sincerity and sensitivity.

 Eneko Osaba – TecNALIA: Quantum Optimization: current trends and open opportunities

The goal of this talk was to provide an overview of the current trends in quantum optimization. The quantum-gate-based approaches are highlighted as well as those related to quantum annealing. The main strengths and weaknesses of each paradigm were pointed out, spotlighting current open challenges. These concerns were aligned with the principles and commitment described in the "Talavera Manifesto for Quantum Software Engineering and Programming". In this regard, it should be noted that the quantum computing research community holds complementary interests, presumably as a result of individual areas of knowledge or interest: i) practitioners coming from industrial and applied research groups, which are mostly concerned about quantum computing-based formulations and experiments over more realistic scenarios; ii) researchers coming from quantum physics, usually interested in analysing the hardware performance and reliability; and iii) researchers with backgrounds in traditional artificial intelligence, involved in testing the limits of QC, comparing results, and leveraging fundamentals, heuristics, or shareable-across-platform knowledge. So, one of the main challenges is to build a united community and establish a strong research avenue, which will lay the foundations that will guide research in the coming years.

Besides that, the focus was especially on quantum-classical hybrid approaches.

 Paolo Cremonesi – Politecnico di Milano: Quantum Annealing as the analog version of Quantum Computing

The quantum computing community has shown significant interest in quantum annealing due to its status as commercially available hardware with the largest number of qubits, far surpassing digital hardware based on the gate model.

In this presentation, the architecture of quantum annealers, highlighting the main open challenges in their usage was explored. Described were the programming frameworks and software tools specifically tailored to support quantum annealers. Additionally, considerations related to performance analysis, algorithmic design, and integrating quantum annealing into existing computing infrastructure were discussed. Finally, some examples on how quantum annealers could be used as hardware accelerators in some machine learning problems were provided.

Session 4: Sustainable Software Engineering

 Radu Prodan - University of Klagenfurt: Extreme and Sustainable Graph Processing for Urgent Societal Challenges in Europe

The presentation has discussed the software engineering challenges in the research and development of a next-generation high-performance, scalable, gender-neutral, secure, and sustainable platform for multilingual information processing and reasoning based on the massive graph representation of extreme data.

The presentation has described the software engineering design of an open-source graph processing toolkit of five open-source software tools and FAIR graph datasets covering the sustainable lifecycle of processing extreme data as massive graphs. The tools were focused on holistic usability (from extreme multilingual data ingestion and massive graph creation), automated intelligence (through analytics and reasoning), performance modelling, and environmental sustainability trade-offs supported by credible data-driven evidence across HPC systems and computing continuum.

The presentation has concluded by introducing several complementary use cases that require and benefit from massive graph processing, considering their extreme data properties and coverage of the three sustainability pillars: economy, society, and environment

 David Wallom – University of Oxford: Commonalities, Themes and Take-Home Messages

In this final wrap-up, the participants collectively took the measure of the workshop and its common emerging threads and resulted in a highly interactive session.

The session aimed to inspire innovative approaches and promote policies supporting software sustainability. As well, this session highlighted the importance of maintaining and adapting software in dynamic environments. It showcased tools and methodologies to enhance software sustainability and emphasised the need for technical and policy innovations.

4.4 Main takeaways

The workshop concluded with a comprehensive summary of the key takeaways and recommendations gleaned throughout the day.

The SWForum.eu *Way Forward Workshop: Future Challenges in Software Engineering* left attendees powered with innovative strategies to navigate the rapidly evolving software engineering landscape. The primary objective was to collectively explore and chart the path forward to effectively address future challenges in software engineering.

The workshop further encouraged collaboration through interactive question-and-answer times in every session. The lively exchanges of ideas and experiences fostered an environment of collaboration, enabling participants to gain valuable insights and fresh perspectives.

Moreover, the SWForum.eu Way Forward Workshop provided an invaluable networking opportunity for attendees. Participants seized the chance to connect with fellow professionals, establish industry contacts, and explore potential research collaborations. The event fostered an environment conducive to building lasting relationships among like-minded individuals passionate about shaping the future of software engineering.

“Software is more pervasive than ever and therefore we need to push together the European research in software engineering. Current technology challenges such as generative AI, Quantum shift paradigm, constrained computing resources in the edge, and cybersecurity for complex software supply chains are highly impacting the way we develop and operate software.” Said Juncal Alonso, from TecNALIA, and SWForum.eu Project Coordinator.

All the participants, speakers, and supporters contributed to the success of this event. The outcomes of the workshop, including the identification of key challenges and the sharing of best practices, will undoubtedly have a lasting impact on the field of software engineering.

The participants in the event had the opportunity to explore the highlights of the sessions and take advantage to download the complete presentations and gain valuable resources to navigate future challenges in software engineering with efficacy.

Ultimately, SwForum.eu will prepare a post-workshop report, scheduled for release in September 2023. This report will provide a comprehensive overview of the workshop, including key insights and actionable recommendations.

5 Lessons Learnt

From the experience gathered organizing a sequence of workshops we have understood that the blend of keynote speakers and open calls seems to work better than just an open call. This is the case, in particular, when the speakers are well-known. This confirms also that the research fellowship programme we have put in place as part of the project is a very useful one, as it allows us to host well-known speakers even during live events.

Through our direct contacts with recognized experts in the field of Software Engineering we were able:

- ❑ To reach the SE community in an efficient way. We brought together a diverse array of professionals who shared their expertise on specific challenges faced by software engineers.
- ❑ To convey the important messages to the SE community. SWForum.eu serves as a catalyst for advancements in software engineering practices.
- ❑ To attract valuable stakeholders and increase their value to the SwForum.eu. They could gain valuable resources to navigate future challenges in software engineering with efficacy.

Based on what we have learned, we think SWForum has the potential to:

- ❑ support long-term community initiatives and substantiate knowledge building and sharing;
- ❑ inspire innovative approaches and promote policies supporting software sustainability.

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6 Conclusions

The SWForum.eu workshops are providing a useful space for researchers, industry representatives, and end users to share their content, knowledge, and informed opinions on the most important software-related issues in the European Research Area. Contributors to the discussion groups can help to determine future directions for Software Technology in Europe.

The *Way Forward* Workshop, in particular, was important event for discussion of the future challenges in Software Engineering:

- Security in the Computing Continuum
- Software Engineering and AI
- Software Engineering for Quantum Computing
- Sustainable Software Engineering

In addition, by bringing together academia, industry, and research organisations, SWForum.eu serves as a catalyst for advancements in software engineering practices.

We look forward to the continued engagement of the experts as we advance in the field of software engineering.

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Appendix A

Graphically enhanced reports generated summarizing some of the sessions of some of the workshops are included as external pdf reports to this document:

Open Source Workshops for computing and Sustainability

PostConferencereport_Mar2023_ExecSum.pdf

PostConferencereportWS2.1_Mar2023.pdf

PostConferencereportWS1.1_Mar2023.pdf

Way Forward Workshop

PostConferencereport_Jul2023_ExecSum.pdf

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Open Source Workshops for Computing & Sustainability

Conference Report

March 2023

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Executive Summary

The Commission has been supporting Open Source foundations and communities for several years and is now engaged in mainstreaming this support in policy development as an important contributor to the value chain, essential for opening up areas of the Digital Economy that otherwise might be in the hands of powerful commercial interests. Open Source drives **competition, innovation and interoperability**, lowering barriers to new entry and providing new ways of using older technologies. Open Source is essential for achieving European **digital autonomy**, but not to cut itself off from the global economy; on the contrary, it will provide Europe with a strong leading position in that open global digital economy.

Open Source software has been historically focused in the software layer and it has become mainstream across all sectors of the software industry during the last 10 years. The impact on the innovation and economic growth has been confirmed by relevant contributions to the economy and wider adoption of Open Source solutions across all industries and society. With the increasing importance of the computing continuum the Open Source paradigm is getting importance throughout the whole computing stack and this is reflected by upcoming RISC-V Instruction Set Open Standard Architecture, boosting innovation and open architectures for processors. Comparably to the well-known benefits in the software community, Open Source hardware opens up highly innovation models and opportunities enlarging the creation of impact in the Computing Continuum.

The EC continues fostering the compromise on promoting the open discussion and constituency cross fertilization to discuss relevant topics for Europe such as OS based solutions that support the **European Digital Transformation**. Therefore, the event entitled “Open Source Workshops for Computing and Sustainability” was organized by the EC -CONNECT and DIGIT units, and held in Brussels on the 2nd of December 2022 with the support of the Software CSA SWForum.eu. It was the continuation of the work started by the EC in the conference “*Open Source Beyond 2020 - Powering a Digital Europe*”¹. The organization of such an event reinforces the EC commitment in promoting and fostering the adoption of OS based solutions that support the European Digital Transformation, especially in the context of:

- ➔ Development of the Data Economy, linked to the development of Artificial Intelligence networks under European values and supported by fair rules such as the Data Act, which will guarantee users control over their data, and open standards, which will avoid vendor lock-in while fostering data interoperability and enabling seamless change of provider.
- ➔ Recognizing the economic potential of adopting OS solutions for the digital transformation of European society and industry. With the “lead by example” approach, the EC is boosting the usage and adoption of OS solutions in local and national public administrations.
- ➔ Guiding and easing the adoption of OS solutions through the development of a rulebook to support, both from the PA perspective and user perspective, the adoption of OS solutions.

“Open Source Workshops for Computing and Sustainability” were organised in the form of interdisciplinary sessions focused on different domains and digital transformation key enabling technologies such as Computing Continuum, Artificial Intelligence and Quantum Computing, with the objective of leveraging the power of Open Source Software and Open Source Hardware to increase the European sovereignty, digital autonomy and advance towards a sustainable ecosystem of intensive software companies and public administrations relying on open and sustainable software solutions.

The programme was designed based on topic focused participatory workshops, with the participation of EC representatives and relevant stakeholders from the different domains conforming the Open Source community, user companies and public administrations looking for sharing experience and driving the actions towards the next generation of OS based technologies and digital services.

1 <https://joinup.ec.europa.eu/collection/eu-fossa-2/event/open-source-beyond-2020-powering-digital-europe>

More specifically, the event was focused on:

- ➔ Open Source for building an Open Computing Architecture from the processor to the applications
- ➔ The role of Open Source as an innovation enabler and sustainable business support
- ➔ Open Source contribution towards the European Digital Sovereignty and Digital Autonomy
- ➔ Economic impact of Open source in the industry and in the public sector towards the open global economy

The event was organized in one opening session followed by two keynote talks. The main slots were organized in 3 workshops sessions, with four parallel workshops each.

In Figure 1 the overview of the workshops session is shown:

WORKSHOP	ROOM	TIME
WS1.1 – OS Processors for the Cloud Continuum	0A	10:00 11:30
WS1.2 – The role of OSS in Artificial Intelligence enabled systems	3B	
WS1.3 – Building Sustainable OS Ecosystems for an Interoperable Europe	1A	
WS1.4 – Identifying, fixing and managing critical OSS used by European Public Services	0C	
WS2.1 – OS Software and Cloud Services and applications	0A	12:00 13:30
WS2.2 – The potential of the symbiosis of Quantum Computing and OSS	3B	
WS2.3 – Encouraging OS business applications reuse via the creation of an EU wide applications Catalogue for European Public Services	1A	
WS2.4 – Exploring how the European public sector can cooperate and act together to solve key OS issues they face	0C	
WS3.1 – Open Standards and industrial use of Open Source	0A	14:30 16:00
WS3.2 – Towards a trustworthy and secure ecosystem of OSS	3B	
WS3.3 – Agreeing, measuring and encouraging organizational contribution to OS ecosystem	1A	
WS3.4 – Exploring practical solutions to ensure long term sustainability of OSS	0C	

Figure 1. Open Source workshops session. See the complete agenda in Appendix A.

All the sessions were chaired by European Commission representatives (or supporting initiatives invited such as the SWForum.eu or QUCATS CSAs) who along with the panellists (3 to 5 per session) managed each workshop actively promoting the participation by the attendees invited. In the following paragraphs the main conclusions per workshop have been summarized.

WS1.1- Open Source Processors for the Cloud Continuum (Chair: Luis Carlos Busquets / CNECT-E2)

Open Source software initiatives have produced a full stack that goes all the way down to the kernel level – but below that, much or all is still closed. Open Source Instruction Set Architectures (ISAs) are becoming increasingly attractive – in particular, RISC-V is gaining much momentum. Integrating Open Source ISAs below the kernel level will make it possible to deploy European technology (e.g., emerging from the European Processor Initiative) in its infrastructures and become digitally autonomous. Only RISC-V currently fulfils that requirement, and for that reason, is a promising ISA for Europe to adopt. Gaps must still be filled around the RISC-V architecture, including missing memory interfaces, communications IP such as PCI Express, and a European standard socket definition. There are special requirements also on cloud server processors (such as support for virtual machines). The concept of a “chipllets market” is a promising way forward to build a thriving European RISC-V ecosystem, exploiting the capabilities of Europe’s innovative but resource-strapped SMEs to combine Open Source with targeted products in a “mix and match” chiplets context. Although similar in concept, Open Source software and hardware have very different costs of production, and the provision of funding to Open Source hardware developers (rather than companies) will be even more critical to the emergence of a thriving Open Source hardware ecosystem in Europe.

WS1.2-The role of OSS in Artificial Intelligence enabled systems: Speeding the AI adoption through OSS (Chair: Miguel Esteras /SWForum.eu)

AI has acquired a strategic stature within the vision of the European Commission, and a multi-pronged set of objectives is evolving based upon not only technological considerations but also policy-oriented considerations such as ethical issues in AI. OS has the potential to make significant contributions to each of these objectives. Technologically, much of current AI research, and especially the sub-discipline of Machine Learning (ML), makes use of large, mature Open Source components (TensorFlow, etc.). ML also makes heavy use of large datasets for training of the neural networks, and here the principles of Open Data can promote the widespread availability of datasets in all sectors of ML application, ranging from language processing to machine vision. The use of OS software and hardware to make available open platforms / testbeds / facilities for testing AI based applications is also an important challenge to explore. Availability of data is going to be a challenge (also with 5G) and therefore data space design principles are needed as well as a common OS infrastructure in Europe for data spaces, i.e., Gaia-X.

WS1.3- Building Sustainable Open Source Ecosystems for an Interoperable Europe. How can we create a sustainable Open -Source ecosystem to support the new intergovernmental cooperation framework in the Interoperable Europe Act? (Chair: Leontina Sandu / DIGIT D2), and Monika Sowinska / DIGIT)

Open Source Observatory (OSOR), serves as a place where the Open Source software community can come together to publish news, find out about events, find relevant OS software solutions, and read about the use of free and Open Source in public administrations across and beyond Europe.

Important question is how we can create a sustainable OS ecosystem to support the new intergovernmental cooperation framework in the Interoperable Europe Act. Particular focus of the workshop is put on the areas where collaboration with OS stakeholders is needed. The Interoperable Europe Act's main objective is to help EU and Member State administrations to deliver connected digital services to citizens and businesses across the EU. The Act helps to raise awareness, and very clearly outlines the why of OS, not just from the public sector perspective, but also with regard to the broader ecosystem (including the private sector). Now that the Act is released, some challenges arise. First of all, it is important to understand how to put forward the actions that are necessary to promote OS. Besides, having OS software regulation is essential and it could help in prioritising things internally.

WS1.4- Identifying, fixing and managing critical Open Source software used by European Public Services (Chair: Miguel Diez Blanco / DIGIT and Saranjit Arora / EC OSPO)

There are thousands of Open Source Software (OSS) components integrated into critical software in European Public Services. These Open Source components often lack the plan for sustaining these projects long-term. This can put important software at a critical stage where maintaining them becomes a challenge.

Major challenges to critical software include the ubiquity and longevity of free OSS, societal role in the development and maintenance of OSS, and the procurement and contracts of individual contributors involved in designing OSS.

Several approaches can be taken to addressing the problem, understanding the supply chain management to address the longevity of critical software being one of the major steps. Furthermore, by obliging Open Source vendors to disclose their OSS, an increased level of transparency and longevity support can be obtained.

WS2.1 – Open Source Software and Cloud Services and Applications: On the way to more interoperable cloud services (Chair: Leire Orue-Echevarria / EC CONNECT)

Data-related legislation is critical to cloud markets, but several legal obstacles remain, also across regional and international divides; Open Source is an instrument for Europe to counteract the debilitating effects of these legal obstacles. Regulatory actions can raise or lower the barriers to switching cloud services; pro-competitive regulation (such as the second Payment Services Directive and the Digital Markets Act, which focuses on interoperability), is an effective tool for counteracting such barriers. The proposed Data Act is another potentially effective tool for ensuring interoperability in Cloud services, but it is imperative that civil society and Open Source providers engage in the

discussions around the Data Act (as they did for the Digital Markets Act) in order to ensure that its provisions are not progressively weakened by interested parties. European market actors have an opportunity to exploit the natural federation of distributed regions in Europe to deploy a new cloud-edge paradigm to support innovative business models for services composed from building blocks offered by small, creative entities in the European SME ecosystem. For Open Source cloud providers to succeed, the existence and health of a significant community is an essential factor. A set of vital research challenges must also be addressed, including continuum-native software, edge-native software, new federated workflows, and collaborative edge systems.

WS2.2 – The potential of the symbiosis of Quantum Computing and OSS: Development of quantum computing OS algorithms and software (Chair: Fanny Bouton / OVHCloud)

Due to its incipient stage of development, Quantum Computing is hybrid by nature. It offers a specialized form of computing power which needs to co-exist with classical architectures in the form of hybrid computing approaches. Therefore, interoperability and reusability are key aspects to take into consideration. A hybrid quantum stack will require management and orchestration to ensure that programs, experiments, processes, and technologies run smoothly and are interoperable. In this context, OS can and should play a relevant role in the future of the Quantum ecosystem, especially from the hardware and software perspectives. In this context, at European level specialization in certain domains (such as chemistry or biology) is seen as the correct strategy to follow in order to compete with other big players and take advantage of the momentum that the frameworks of these big players are creating around the software developer community. The need for the creation of a network serving a European Quantum community could also leverage on existing OS communities to foster cooperation, collaboration and networking between the main European players.

WS2.3 – Encouraging Open Source business applications reuse via the creation of an EU wide Applications Catalogue for European Public Services (Chair: Evangelos Tsavalopoulos / DIGIT B3.002 and Saranjit Arora / EC OSPO)

Public administrations across Europe have over the years built a huge number of business applications using Open Source software tools. Despite this, we continue to rebuild the same types of applications across the EU. A catalog could save millions of Euros and allow faster solution realisation.

Recently the DIGIT unit at the EC has been collaborating with the EU Parliament to build such a European catalog, which is expected to be ready in June 2023. However, this product is not standalone – it will be necessary to integrate information from existing catalogs. Proper and timely updates of the information at a central level will be an important issue to confront.

Some takeaways from the workshop are the importance of measuring the success of the European application catalog, building a community around the catalog, ranking the software, standards, etc. Also, it is essential to understand which approach is better: centralisation or federation. Much remains to be done – many people are willing to reuse the software. However, some OSS products should be open only to certain PA authorities.

WS2.4 – Encouraging Open Source business applications reuse via the creation of an EU wide Applications Catalogue for European Public Services (Chair: Gijs Hillenius /DIGIT and Miguel Diez Blanco / DIGIT)

Development, procurement and maintenance of OSS in the European public sector is a challenging activity in which knowledge and experiences sharing is a key factor to foster the reuse of Open Source business applications in the public sector.

Major challenges to this respect include, the effective and efficient functioning of technology and policy together, the lack of political vision around Open Source, long-term collaboration, and the long-term sustainability of such projects. The knowledge culture and lack of steering of Open Source projects is also part of the problem. The lack of political vision and understanding of Open Source models is key. This snowballs into the lack of people in the organization who understand how policy and technology work together and know how to tackle these kinds of problems.

Several approaches can be adopted to address these challenges and the difficulties faced while working on open shared projects (i.e., ground-up approach vs. a top-down) but the direct involvement of politicians in making decisions about the development and procurement of OSS is a recognised requirement. Special focus is to be put on the international collaboration (and not only within each member state), fostering publicly funded Open Source initiatives (i.e., Erasmus program for Open Source developers), and increased awareness and urgency in the public about Open Source potentials and impact in the daily live.

WS3.1 – Open standards and industrial use for Open Source: Leveraging the sustainability of Open Source projects and increasing competition and interoperability between different steps in value-chains (Chair: John Favaro / SWForum.eu)

Company policies towards Open Source embrace the use of and contribution to software that is crucial for its products. Raising awareness of OS possibilities has been identified as an effective policy for increasing economic growth. OS assets facilitate making an efficient use of resources and increase industrial competitiveness. Together with standards they are embedded in nearly all electronic devices we use in our daily live. Computers, TVs, electrical appliances, phones, cars are using millions of lines of code from projects initially started by hundreds of volunteer developers and shared with all. Also, many OS projects implement open standards.

However, there are different expectations about what open standards are (i.e., more examples of Open Source implementations of open standards) and can do and a unified definition at European level is needed. Small organizations need help to deal with the regulations, and the EC could help them in this process. Also, the adoption of Open Source software while actively addressing the associated need for adopting open standards should be led through EC mandates. Software developers should be invited together with other bigger players to set up and participate in the discussion tables promoting “bottom up” approaches for the open standards creation processes (following the “de facto” standards strategy) focusing on implementing first; seeing what works; and shaping standards from the proven implementation.

WS3.2 – Towards a trustworthy and secure ecosystem of OSS: Increasing the reliability and adoption of OSS projects (Chair: James Galand-Jones / EC-Connect)

From the surveys conducted by the EC as part of the study “*The impact of Open Source Software and Hardware on technological independence, competitiveness and innovation in the EU economy*” cybersecurity and trustworthiness of OSS and OSH was of significant importance. A particular concern identified is related to the ability of chips or software components to incorporate backdoors or malware embedded by a bad actor in the supply chain. The ability to develop and maintain a root of trust, through the supply chain is facilitated by open hardware and software. This impact will increase over time.

The detection of cybersecurity attacks needs to be addressed from a holistic point of view with the incorporation of best practices, new processes, and tools to prevent attacks. The upcoming CRA legislation has the objective of increasing the cyber resilience of software and hardware artifacts, manufactured, developed, and operated in Europe, including commercial Open Source projects. Of course, the CRA needs to consider the special nature of Open Source as a frictionless collaboration, and to preserve the innovative character of European actors in the application of the CRA, reflecting the complexity of the OS world.

WS3.3 – Agreeing, measuring and encouraging organisational contribution to the Open Source ecosystem (Chair: Saranjit Arora / EC OSPO and Miguel Diez Blanco / DIGIT B3.002)

Open Source (OS) is a vital infrastructure to our digital world, pervading every personal device and business system we use. Both the private and public sectors continue to increase their use of OS, which is a positive trend. However, on the whole, the existence, availability, and support of OS are taken for granted. Many individuals, companies, foundations, and public administrations do contribute, but the current level of contribution is already recognised to be insufficient. Essential questions that rise are: How can we measure the organisation’s contribution to OS? How does a conscientious organisation know it is contributing enough? Are there contribution best practices? Contribution is really vital to the

sustainability of the OS, and potentially of even greater benefit to the contributing organisation.

In particular, this workshop focuses on OS business applications reuse via the creation of an EU-wide applications catalog for European public services. Furthermore, it regards how European companies and public services contribute to OS today and debates what they should do in terms of best practices. The impact such contribution has on organisations that contribute enthusiastically is also discussed.

Besides, it is essential to put into place legislation frameworks, in order to avoid reinventing something that already exists.

WS3.4 – Exploring practical solutions to ensure long term sustainability of Open Source software (Chair: Chrysanthi Giortsou / DY and Gijs Hillenius / DIGIT)

Most software, once released into the market, is forgotten about and the community around maintaining OSS is not as robust at the moment. Furthermore, the lack of access to funding for small projects and businesses to develop and maintain such infrastructure proves to be a challenge.

There are quite a few small-scale projects that aren't identified by the EC that need support through their development cycle. Moreover, many such projects are undermined by medium-to-large scale projects as most of the funding and support is eaten by them. This presents an opportunity for the involvement of governments and large organizations to put more attention on funding the individual's effort and support existing projects.

There is funding available for innovation but not for the people who maintain those innovations. The lack of long-term outlook and planning for OSS and the funding mechanisms in place that don't always fit the product needs poses a large challenge in understanding the long-term sustainability of an OSS. By addressing the employment of people to maintain these services while supporting them through the development process would be quite essential in getting these services running in the long-term.

DRAFT

Open Source Workshops for Computing & Sustainability

WS1.1

Open-Source Processors for the Cloud Continuum

March 2023

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WS1.1 – Open Source Processors for the Cloud Continuum

Open Source Workshops for Computing & Sustainability
2 December 2022
Albert Borschette Congress Center (CCAB), Brussels

Workshop 1.1 OS Processors
Open Source Processors for the Cloud Continuum | 10:00 - 11:30 CET

Chair
Luis C. Busquets Pérez
EC-CONNECT, European Commission

Panellists

- John Davis
BSC
- Roger Espasa
Semidynamics
- Andrea Acquaviva
University of Bologna
- Olof Kindgren
Qamcom Technology AB and FOSSI Foundation
- Patrick Pype
NXP and RISC-V Open Source Working Group
- Craig Prunty
SiPearl VP Marketing & Business Development

Figure 1. Workshop chair and panellists.

In the last 20 years, Open Source has become pervasive in all the ICT industry. Open Source Software needs to be considered while designing the business strategy of any company in the ICT sector. On the other hand, Open Source hardware is in terms of adoption in a similar position as OSS was a decade from now.

The success from OSS has come with the availability of a flexible Open stack from the kernel to the application level. This stack ensures digital autonomy to the EU in the layers it covers. The extension of the stack below the kernel in the HTC sector would carry the Digital autonomy to layers where Europe is today not independent. The aforementioned extension to the processor level will increase the threads and opportunities that Europe will need to address increasing the need of a detailed analysis on the weaknesses to overcome and the strengths Europe can count on.

As early as 2019, it had already been observed that Open Source software initiatives had produced a full stack that went all the way down to the kernel level – but below that, much or all was closed. Open Source Instruction Set Architectures (ISAs) are becoming increasingly attractive – in particular, RISC-V is gaining much momentum.

The question before us now is how we can integrate Open Source ISAs below the kernel level to allow us to deploy European technology in our infrastructures and become digitally autonomous. The outcomes of the European Processor Initiative are very relevant not only for the discussion of today, but also if we want to build European Cloud infrastructures run by European technology.

Although the concept of an Instruction Set Architecture (ISA) is well known in the community, the concept of an Open-Source ISA is less well clarified. The envisioned characteristics for such an Open Source ISA are:

- ➔ It can be implemented without a license;
- ➔ It can be extended without a license;
- ➔ It is not controlled by a single company.

Currently, only RISC-V fulfils that requirement, and for that reason, is a promising ISA for Europe to adopt as part of its strategy to ensure its future digital sovereignty. As a contrast, the case of ARM can be noted, which is controlled by an

external entity, and is currently embroiled in a [lawsuit](#) with Qualcomm over licensing rights. (Qualcomm has recently begun to [consider](#) RISC-V as an alternative to ARM.)

Another relevant concept to be clarified is that of an Open Source processor for cloud servers. There are indeed special features needed for cloud server processors, such as great support for virtual machines, and good power management and security – including the guarantee of no foreign backdoors (once again, the concept of not being controlled by an outside entity).

In fact, the very definition of “Open Source hardware” can be questioned and “Open Source silicon” may well be a better definition, because both hardware and software are involved in chip design, and a proper legal framework for this would draw from the legal frameworks of both hardware and software.

RISC-V concept and current situation. RISC-V has a recognized importance in supporting the European strategy for digital sovereignty also below the kernel. Much of the current development is being carried out by members of the European Processor Initiative. Although much has been done up until now, there are many components that could be added. For example, the core is there, but some parts of it must still be bought today. There are also several potential components outside the CPU itself that can and should be made available – much like a car engine still needs its “peripherals” like wheels and exhaust pipes to interact with the outside world. Thus, an important objective would be to fill in the gaps, such as missing memory interfaces, and communications IP like PCI Express. One item of particular interest would be the definition of a European open standard socket for cloud processors. Open socket definitions are important for generation-over-generation reuse. But there are also other gaps, such as missing EDA tooling and verification tools.

Overall, it could be stated that “all the building blocks are there”, but we need to find a way to realize the vision.

The way ahead for RISC-V. Several actions can and should be taken to realize the European vision of an Open Source ISA contributing to its digital sovereignty. Here again, the experience of ARM, along with other processors such as SPARC needs to be considered and learnt from. The success of ARM versus other processors was in its ability to create an ecosystem (whereas the others were always in the hands of very few companies). The challenge for RISC-V will be to likewise create a thriving ecosystem of actors all serving a RISC-V market. One possibility would be the emergence of a “chiplets market”, where actors in the ecosystem can contribute, and users can mix and match solutions. Such a “chiplet marketplace” is one way in which small companies can compete with larger players, a strength of the European industry where SMEs and start-ups have always been particularly prominent in providing innovative solutions. The lack of a licensing fee for RISC-V is also an enabler for SMEs and start-ups, who are usually strapped with low financial resources. A thriving ecosystem with many actors means that, as the server market grows, some of them can now start to specialize: storage processors, or HPC processors, or a low-end, low-power processor for edge applications (all of which have different architectural requirements). As a result, we will start to see different solutions in the growing market.

Another key concept is to utilize Open Source strategically for the very purpose of growing the ecosystem. As an example, PCI Express is what might be called “high value / low differentiation”. That is, it is needed by all, but does not provide significant competitive differentiation. By making an Open Source version available to all, more actors are spared the expense of developing or buying their own, and can concentrate on the value-adding elements of their own competitive proposition, thus mitigating the costs of entering and participating in the ecosystem.

What can be Open Sourced below the kernel? open sourcing seemed to arrive at the Verilog level, but never quite seemed to arrive at the level of the silicon. Some of the reasons for this are:

- ➔ It is indeed the case that the Register Transfer Level (RTL) can, and should be, Open Source. There is no problem at this level. However:
- ➔ At the level of design verification, all the companies have restrictions and NDAs on their interfaces – and so it cannot be Open Sourced.
- ➔ Consider now the CAD level, and the Process Design Kits (PDKs): Open PDKs do exist; but for the ones we currently care about (e.g., for lower geometries below 45 nm), they are all proprietary, under NDA, and cannot be Open Sourced.
- ➔ The libraries that go into the PDKs for the standard cells are also proprietary / under NDA and cannot be Open Sourced.

Thus, it is the current ecosystem that prevents us from open sourcing the RTL (Register Transfer Level) to GDS (Graphic Data Stream or Graphic Design System) flow (also simply called the “RTL2GDS flow”). Effectively, the industry is currently resisting open sourcing at these levels.

Indeed, there is still difference between Open Source hardware and Open Source software. Software is in many ways just as expensive as hardware, if not more. But software does have one advantage: updates and improvements can be integrated very quickly with today’s highly automated workflows. An Open Source software provider can have a competitive strategy that allows it to provide new features every six months, deprecating old features – all with the touch of a button on its DevOps system. This is simply not possible with hardware, at least in the foreseeable future. Changes to hardware can involve millions of Euros. And so, it will remain a challenge to find ways to imitate the success of software in this type of competitive strategy in a hardware context.

Funding instruments need to be created for funding Open Source hardware development . In fact, much of the seemingly low-cost of Open Source software is derived from the fact that so much software development is contributed by software developers in their free time, without pay. But in the case of hardware, this is far less possible, even if it were desirable, because of the inherent high costs of hardware development and delivery. We must fund *developers* rather than big companies, enabling affordable fabrication of our chips in order to realize our vision of a thriving Open Source hardware ecosystem in Europe.

In summary. Open Source software initiatives have produced a full stack that goes all the way down to the kernel level – but below that, much or all is still closed. Open Source Instruction Set Architectures (ISAs) are becoming increasingly attractive – in particular, RISC-V is gaining much momentum. Integrating Open Source ISAs below the kernel level will make it possible to deploy European technology (e.g., emerging from the European Processor Initiative) in its infrastructures and become digitally autonomous. Only RISC-V currently fulfils that requirement, and for that reason, is a promising ISA for Europe to adopt. Gaps must still be filled around the RISC-V architecture, including missing memory interfaces, communications IP such as PCI Express, and a European standard socket definition. There are special requirements also on cloud server processors (such as support for virtual machines). The concept of a “chiplets market” is a promising way forward to build a thriving European RISC-V ecosystem, exploiting the capabilities of Europe’s innovative but resource-strapped SMEs to combine Open Source with targeted products in a “mix and match” chiplets context. Although similar in concept, Open Source software and hardware have very different costs of production, and the provision of funding to Open Source hardware developers (rather than companies) will be even more critical to the emergence of a thriving Open Source hardware ecosystem in Europe.

WS1.1 Video

[OPEN SOURCE WORKSHOPS FOR COMPUTING AND SUSTAINABILITY \(0A\) - Streaming Service of the European Commission \(europa.eu\)](#)

From minute 10:17 to minute 11:57.

WS1.1 Presentations

- ➔ Topics on Open Source Processors for Cloud Continuum – Craig Prunty
- ➔ A CPU is only as good as its ecosystem – Olof Kindgren
- ➔ Open Source Computing System. The RISC-V way – Andrea Acquaviva
- ➔ Open Source Processors for the Cloud Continuum – Patrick Pype
- ➔ Open Source Processors for the Cloud Continuum – Roger Espasa

Open Source Workshops for Computing & Sustainability

WS2.1

Open-Source Software and
Cloud Services and
Applications: On the way to
more interoperable cloud
services

March 2023

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WS2.1 – Open Source Software and Cloud Services and Applications: On the way to more interoperable cloud services

The banner for Workshop 2.1 OSS for Cloud Continuum features a light blue background with a grid pattern. At the top left, it reads 'Open Source Workshops for Computing & Sustainability' with a calendar icon and the date '2 December 2022' and location 'Albert Borschette Congress Center (CCAB), Brussels'. Logos for the European Commission and SWForum.eu are on the right. The workshop title 'Workshop 2.1 OSS for Cloud Continuum' and time '12:00 - 13:30 CET' are prominently displayed. Below this is the subtitle 'Open Source Software and Cloud Services and Applications: On the way to more interoperable cloud services'. The 'Chair' section features a circular portrait of Leire Orúe-Echevarría from EC-CONNECT. The 'Panellists' section features six circular portraits: Josef Urban (Nokia Bell Labs and NESSI), Frank Karlitschek (NextCloud), Astor Nummelin Carlberg (OpenForumEurope), Maria Fazio (University of Messina), and Alberto P. Martí (OpenNebula). A large 'DRAFT' watermark is overlaid diagonally across the center.

Figure 1. Workshop 2.1 chair and panellists

According to a study carried out by the European Commission, companies in the EU invested around 1 billion Euros in Open Source Software (OSS) in 2018¹, which amounted to an economic impact of 65 to 95 million Euros. The same study estimates that an increase of 10% of OSS contributions would annually generate an additional increase of 0.4% to 0.6% in the GDP.

The adoption of cloud computing by the industry can accelerate the commoditization of Open Source software. Several OSS solutions exist to solve specific challenges that can be found in the cloud continuum services stack. Cloud vendors, especially the large ones, are monetizing OSS by integrating it into their own cloud services proprietary derivatives created by them, but few release them as Open Source or they do it under a very complicated licensing model.

End-to-end integration of the whole cloud stack and easier exit cloud switching options horizontally (between cloud services of the same type) and vertically (between layers of the cloud stack) are amongst the most critical challenges that need to be solved for the cloud continuum to be successful. This can only be achieved by making Open Source technologies available by each cloud and edge service provider, allowing for portability and simplifying the switch among cloud continuum services. This calls for communities that wish to create open technologies which are part of larger ecosystems, and which together aim to create full stack solutions.

Challenges and opportunities of releasing cloud services as Open Source. The hyperscalers (and others) often use Open Source as their baseline code, while very few then release the services as Open Source, thereby returning them

¹ European Commission, Directorate-General for Communications Networks, Content and Technology, Blind, K., Pättsch, S., Muto, S., et al., The impact of Open Source software and hardware on technological independence, competitiveness and innovation in the EU economy: final study report, Publications Office, 2021, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2759/430161>

to the community. These actions results in several problems that need to be addressed by the involved stakeholders. In addition, the usage of Open Source can also help to solve relevant issues such as cloud service switching, and interoperability – in short, the many interlocking issues permeating the cloud continuum.

Looking at the landscape of members of the “Cloud Native Computing Foundation” (CNCF), it becomes clear that Open Source is considered to be an innovation engine especially in the cloud computing area. We could go far as to say that “cloud native” is *defined* by Open Source. Yet, Open Source must be viewed in a balanced fashion. This view is reflected in recent [publications](#), and identifies five key criteria to assess concerning the use of Open Source in one’s organization: Total Cost of Ownership; Reuse; Community; Security; Licensing.

Legal and regulatory issues. If “data is the new oil”, then data-related legislation is critical to cloud markets, which deal so intensively in data. Here, the legal situation is quite fluid. Although Safe Harbor Agreements were established between the U.S. and Europe as early as 2000, the situation has evolved since then in such a way that the 2016 European GDPR and the 2018 U.S. [CLOUD Act](#) are incompatible. Even the latest [agreement](#) signed by Presidents Biden and von der Leyen is probably not valid. Current legal initiatives in Europe and the U.S. are in fact going in different directions (Europe toward more protection, U.S. toward less). Doubling down on Open Source could be a way for Europe to counteract the debilitating effects of these legal obstacles. Likewise, regulatory actions can raise or lower the barriers to switching cloud services for users. Networked markets (such as the Continuum) have network effects where winner takes all – and therefore create less competition. So-called pro-competitive regulation is a useful tool in counteracting this phenomenon. As an example of pro-competitive regulation in Europe, the second Payment Services Directive has enabled the user to switch banks more easily. Another example is the Digital Markets Act – strengthening interoperability functionalities, whereby new alternative services may be created (through mandated interoperability), and therefore more competition is enabled. As a final example, the Data Act (proposed in February 2022) is currently being negotiated: this Act is strongly focused on ensuring interoperability in Cloud services, because interoperability, together with Open Source and standards, is the key to enabling competitive alternatives. The Data Act introduces minimum requirements for Cloud Switching. It is of course difficult to predict when the negotiations on the Data Act will finish (and there are also national negotiations underway). Using the Digital Markets Act for comparison, the negotiations went quickly, lasting only about one year. The current prediction for enactment of the Data Act is approximately 2024. However, civil society is currently not paying enough attention to the Data Act (whereas the attention of civil society was key to the passage of the interoperability provisions of the Digital Markets Act). Likewise, Open Source cloud providers are not paying sufficient attention and should join the negotiations for creating the final Data Act, because this is their opportunity.

Federation – opportunities for Europe. The nature of Europe as a federation of distributed regions with no central authority could produce opportunities for Europe if harnessed effectively. One driver can be open standards, which allow these distributed regions to interact and collaborate. Decentralization is a likely evolution of the cloud market, because it is unlikely that in the future all of the data in the world will be held in only a few enormous data centres. Here, the concept of the cloud-edge continuum is an enabler, where Europe has an opportunity to take the lead and bring back balance to the cloud market and take a leadership position in critical technological areas. Europe needs to leverage this opportunity to go from a highly centralized cloud paradigm to a decentralized edge paradigm. European companies are already preparing new products and services for this new paradigm that promise to offer real alternatives to the current hyperscalers, including innovative new business models. For example, one can imagine two alternatives for providing services in the Continuum:

- The traditional approach is for providers to provide complete services, using data coming from the edge to the cloud, e.g., from IoT devices. This is a more “monolithic” approach, where providers compete on similar packages of offerings.
- Another approach is related to the idea of the federated ecosystem. Here, different opportunities arrive from different providers, including large and small companies, operating at different levels. In such an approach, what matters to the customer is how these different services can be combined to offer something new in the market.

This second, “federated and process-centred” approach creates opportunities for end users to be independent from specific providers and being able to automate processes to compose services that exactly match what they need. In the market, this approach produces “process innovation” – that is, producers of Cloud services that fill a gap in future, innovative processes. Innovative start-ups and SMEs can also compete effectively in such a market paradigm,

another advantage for Europe. Certainly, there are technical challenges involved, such as the composition of stateless microservices, as well as issues of orchestration and resource management. This represents the challenge of “Intelligent automation”. Nevertheless, Open Source has already given us much of the components we need to address that challenge.

Research challenges. Several research challenges are still to be overcome with regard to the Cloud, including: cognitive computing using AI, Intent-driven management, multi-agent distributed intelligence, preparation and sharing of data (a topic addressed also in other sessions), and *Continuum-native software*, which may be seen as an evolution of “cloud-native software engineering”. In addition, we need different workflows and technologies from those of monolithic systems in order to accomplish our goals for “federated” workflows. Another research challenge is how to create collaborative edge systems that can work together to provide localized services. Finally, cognitive computing is even more of a challenge at the edge than in the cloud. We need *edge-native* technology now, not just adapted cloud technology.

Cloud providers and Open Source. Why aren't many of today's cloud providers, particularly the hyperscalers, releasing code in Open Source? Is it fear of intellectual property law? Is it related to their business model? There needs to be a win-win situation for all stakeholders in a cloud ecosystem. It needs to be balanced, so that all stakeholder communities can grow and benefit together. In the proprietary world of cloud offerings, there are issues of intellectual property and licenses that create an imbalance among the stakeholders and tend to lead to this phenomenon of not releasing code in Open Source. In the Open Source world, this imbalance does not exist, removing the barriers to a cloud provider releasing in Open Source

Relevant European initiatives are currently underway to realize the vision of a European cloud ecosystem based upon the cloud/edge paradigm:

- ➔ [SovereignEdge.EU](#) is an initiative to explore the question of how far Europe can indeed go in deploying the new continuum paradigm with Open Source technologies and achieving technological sovereignty in some critical technological areas.
- ➔ The [European Alliance for Industrial Data, Edge, and Cloud](#) is now starting up, working on a roadmap for the European cloud industry.
- ➔ The IPCEI on Next Generation Cloud Infrastructure and Services ([IPCEI-CIS](#)) is a joint initiative of twelve Member States under the coordination of Germany and France to enable a Multi-Provider Cloud-Edge Continuum.

In summary. Data-related legislation is critical to cloud markets, but several legal obstacles remain, also across regional and international divides; Open Source is an instrument for Europe to counteract the debilitating effects of these legal obstacles. Regulatory actions can raise or lower the barriers to switching cloud services; pro-competitive regulation (such as the second Payment Services Directive and the Digital Markets Act, which focuses on interoperability), is an effective tool for counteracting such barriers. The proposed Data Act is another potentially effective tool for ensuring interoperability in Cloud services, but it is imperative that civil society and Open Source providers engage in the discussions around the Data Act (as they did for the Digital Markets Act) in order to ensure that its provisions are not progressively weakened by interested parties. European market actors have an opportunity to exploit the natural federation of distributed regions in Europe to deploy a new cloud-edge paradigm to support innovative business models for services composed from building blocks offered by small, creative entities in the European SME ecosystem. For Open Source cloud providers to succeed, the existence and health of a significant community is an essential factor. A set of vital research challenges must also be addressed, including continuum-native software, edge-native software, new federated workflows, and collaborative edge systems.

WS 2.1 Video

[OPEN SOURCE WORKSHOPS FOR COMPUTING AND SUSTAINABILITY \(0A\) - Streaming Service of the European Commission \(europa.eu\)](#)

From minute 12:12 to minute 13:44.

WS2.1 Presentations

- ➔ Open Source Software and the Computing Continuum - Josef Urban
- ➔ 3 big challenges for Europe + and an answer – Frank Karlitschek
- ➔ Policy Approaches to Easing Cloud-Switching – Astor Nummelin
- ➔ OOS to automatize processes in the Continuum – Maria Fazio
- ➔ The Birth of a Geopolitical EU Cloud Industry. Reclaiming Open Source as a Tool for Europe’s Technological Sovereignty – Alberto P. Martí

DRAFT

The Way Forward Workshop on Future Challenges in Software Engineering

27 June 2023 - Milano, Italy

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Disclaimer

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About SWForum.eu

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Executive Summary

The SWForum.eu “Way Forward Workshop on Future Challenges in Software Engineering” took place on 27 June 2023 at the Politecnico di Milano, in the Dipartimento di Elettronica, Informazione e Bioingegneria (DEIB). Its purpose was to bring researchers and practitioners together to assess the current state of software engineering in the context of a set of representative advanced technologies and discuss the resulting challenges that the future will bring in the discipline.

The program committee selected four areas that are considered particularly pertinent at this time.

Security in the Computing Continuum. Security in the computing world is very similar to security in the supply chain world – if one link in the chain or in the process is unsafe or insecure, this can make the whole system or the whole software unsafe or insecure. There have been significant efforts to incorporate “security by design” into software development, but significant challenges likewise remain, including those related to new technologies like machine learning.

Software Engineering and AI. The remarkable worldwide impact of the new Large Language Models is only the latest manifestation of the growing mutual influence that AI and software engineering are exerting on each other. Can current software engineering practices cope with the complexities of AI architectures and applications, including validation (explainability) and security?

Software Engineering for Quantum Computing. Quantum computing is reaching significant and promising advancements and represents one of the ground-breaking initiatives that are expected to change the way we conceive programming today. A crucial issue from the software engineering standpoint is the identification of effective design and programming abstractions that allow people skilled in computer science to take advantage of the enormous power of quantum computing while keeping the complexity of design and programming activities under control and enabling analysis and testing of the developed code.

Sustainable Software Engineering. Sustainability within software is often considered to be how easily or well a particular piece of software can be maintained or developed in the face of changing or developing environments around it. Can the concept be extended to its contribution to urgent challenges such as the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals?

“Software is more pervasive than ever and therefore we need to push together the European research in software engineering. Current technology challenges such as generative AI, Quantum shift paradigm, constrained computing resources in the edge, and cybersecurity for complex software supply chains are highly impacting the way we develop and operate software.”

Juncal Alonso, SWForum.eu Project Coordinator.

The workshop began with an introduction to the SWForum.eu project and its objectives in creating a forum for discussion of software engineering challenges and opportunities within the European software community. It closed with a wrap-up session of conclusions among the participants.

The full agenda of the workshop and speaker presentations may be found on the SWForum.eu website.¹ The results of the individual sessions are summarized in the following sections.

1. <https://swforum.eu/agenda-swforum.eu-way-forward-workshop-future-challenges-software-engineering>

Highlights from the Event

Session 1 09:30 - 10:30

Security in the Computing Continuum

Mark Miller
Conceptivity

CHAIR

The area of cybersecurity is producing new challenges in numerous areas of software engineering. The increasing criticality of cyber-physical systems (e.g., self-driving vehicles, medical equipment, IoT devices) and the growing complexity of the software supply chain is creating challenges for the architecting and development of software systems that interact heavily with the environment and are often connected across the entire cloud-edge continuum. A particularly critical case is power distribution systems, where a successful attack can effectively shut down an entire infrastructure. Legacy power systems are often subsequently connected in unexpected ways, providing originally unforeseen bridges for attackers to access everything downstream in the continuum. New defences are needed, such as frequent changes of interconnections or interactions among system components, to present attackers with moving targets.

Security By Design is a new and compelling paradigm for engineering of secure systems. But in order to become practical in real-world commercial contexts, it needs to incorporate the features that service providers in relevant fields (e.g., telecommunications) are routinely expected offer, such as Service Level Agreements (SLAs). However, features like SLAs for cybersecurity introduce new challenges in software engineering, such as developing meaningful metrics for characterizing levels of security in software systems; such challenges will lead to the development of new and appropriate ways to model systems in order to be able to capture such metrics.

Generative AI is acknowledged to have provided new perspectives on software development (see also Session 2), but it is also making contributions to the toolbox of the malicious cybersecurity actor. Phishing attacks account for the largest portion of cyberattacks, and AI is making these kinds of attacks even more efficient and effective to design. Open-source intelligence (OSINT), gathered from the internet and combined with generative AI, makes it possible to personalise phishing message texts. Multimedia forms of generative AI (e.g., image-from-text systems) are making it possible to design and implement credible websites for phishing attacks. Software cybersecurity engineers will need to develop new techniques to recognize and counteract this new category of AI-enabled attacks – including AI-supported countermeasures.

During the session...

Session Agenda

- Cyber-Physical Systems: Attack and Defence – **1. Martin Higgins**, University of Oxford
- Security-by-Design methodologies and security metrics – **2. Valentina Casola**, University of Napoli Federico II
- Usage of AI to automate human-related cyber attacks – **3. Francesco Morano**, CEFRIEL

Session 2 11:00 - 13:00

Software Engineering and Artificial Intelligence

John Favaro
Trust-IT

CHAIR

Software engineering and AI have been closely coupled for decades. AI-enabled assistance for software engineering has been envisioned for more than thirty years, and with the arrival of generative AI, it now seems feasible not only at the coding level, but at all levels ranging from requirements elicitation to operations and maintenance. The size and complexity of the new AI-enabled systems has also opened up new challenges for software engineering support for the construction of these systems.

One such challenge is the integration of considerations of trustworthiness and ethical values in AI-enabled systems, if they are to be used in critical, industrial-grade applications. In Value-Sensitive Design (VSD), end users and technology developers work together from the very beginning of the engineering cycle to ensure this integration, while generating a statistical model and other general evaluation mechanisms to understand and quantify the satisfaction of ethical and trustworthiness criteria.

A related challenge is the integration of economic considerations in AI-enabled systems, of which one very well-known example is binary classification. Binary classification is often used to separate “good” from “bad” categories in arbitrary domains. However, mistaken classifications (e.g., false positives or false negatives) can have high economic costs – which could be the opposite depending on the domain. By integrating domain-specific (economic) value-based considerations into these AI-enabled systems, their real-world usefulness can be greatly enhanced.

If software engineering can hope to ameliorate the construction of machine learning-based systems, a plausible research agenda must be formulated. Challenges currently being identified for possible inclusion in a research agenda include improving the deployment and operation of federated learning systems in a self-adaptive manner, which in practice involves addressing numerous issues, such as the sharing of private data among the clients and the optimisation of workload and resource allocation. Another example is the automatic detection of unknown domains and adaptation of neural networks to them.

Yet even if these challenges are addressed, a major challenge remains of finding a good paradigm for the integration of software engineering and AI development processes. In an experience with “MLOps”, a phenomenon of two separate teams (ML and DevOps) was observed that did not successfully integrate at the cultural level, each demonstrating little knowledge of or interest in the other culture. This led to costly development errors, such as a drastic underestimation of the amount of support infrastructure needed for MLOps, with consequent rise in technical debt.

Yet another challenge concerning the integration of AI and software engineering is the increasing importance of AI in applications that span the computing continuum. This leads to the need for new software engineering approaches to managing both applications and AI-related activities across the continuum. For example, for the validation and improvement of ML models used on the near and far Edge (e.g., for robotic and automated driving applications), techniques are needed to optimally move data from devices to the cloud to train, validate, and improve AI models to be used in further missions. The concept of a “meta” operating system that can transparently span the continuum is one way of helping to simplify the management of application development and operations in the continuum, including AI-enabled applications.

Another way to help to simplify AI-related development in the continuum is the provision of an advanced framework that fills known technology gaps, by providing solutions to efficiently develop and deploy AI enterprise applications across the computing continuum. The framework contains not only strategically developed tools and components that cover those known gaps, but also a design workflow that pulls together those key tools into a coherent methodology.

During the session...

Session Agenda

- Evaluating and validating hybrid AI algorithms and asserting their adherence to an ethical and legal overarching approach to trustworthiness – **1. Nuria Quintana Fernandez**, TECNALIA
- Software Engineering for Machine Learning, some first experiences – **2. Luciano Baresi**, Politecnico di Milano
- MLOps the hard way: a journey on integrating AI & software engineering – **3. Michele Ciavotta**, University of Milano
- On the evaluation of binary classifiers for Software Engineering – **4. Luigi Lavazza**, Università degli Studi dell’Insubria
- Development of an IoT2cloud Operating System (ICOS) – **5. Marina Giordanino**, Stellantis
- AI-SPRINT: Design and Runtime Framework for Accelerating the Development of AI Applications in the Computing Continuum – **6. Francesco Lattari**, Politecnico di Milano

Session 3 🕒 14:10 - 15:30

Software Engineering for Quantum Computing

Elisabetta Di Nitto
POLIMI

CHAIR

Quantum computing is rapidly leaving the laboratory with the promise of becoming industrially relevant technology. Software engineers are attempting to create a new discipline of “quantum software engineering” for providing new methods, frameworks, and programming languages for quantum applications. A kind of roadmap and call for action has been elaborated in the Talavera Manifesto for Quantum Software Engineering and Programming, which attempts to define and present a set of fundamental principles. Yet survey results indicate that much current research concentrates on software testing, proposals for solutions, and “philosophical” papers rather than more traditional software engineering topics like processes and professional practice.

One area that has garnered considerable interest is quantum optimization, due to its potential to achieve significant improvements over classical approaches, with vast applications ranging from transportation (cf. the famous Traveling Salesman problem) to finance and energy. There is particular interest in hybrid quantum-classical solvers, due to its promise of both performance improvements and dealing with current limited quantum resources. But different research groups are approaching the problem from different perspectives, and still need to form a united community to guide research and avoid fragmentation.

Optimization serves as a good example of the conceptual challenges that quantum computing can present to software engineers used to traditional approaches. While the quantum gate model is closer to the traditional digital computing model, quantum annealing may be seen as an analogue version which, while capable of achieving highly performant results (for example, in optimization problems like the Traveling Salesman), requires programmers to understand the nonintuitive quantum mechanics underlying its behaviour.

During the session...

Session Agenda

- The Quantum Frontier of Software Engineering and its Adoption – **1. Dario Di Nucci**, University of Salerno
- The Role of Formal Probabilistic Models in Quantum Computing – **2. Vlado Stankovski**, University of Ljubljana
- Quantum Optimisation: current trends and open opportunities – **3. Eneko Osaba**, TECNALIA
- Quantum Annealing as the analog version of Quantum Computing – **4. Paolo Cremonesi**, Politecnico di Milano

Session 4 🕒 16:00 - 17:30

Sustainable Software Engineering

David Wallom
University of Oxford

CHAIR

“Sustainable software engineering” is a concept that may be usefully viewed from different perspectives. For example, it may be viewed from the perspective of traditional best practices in development and maintenance in order to remain robust and valid – sustainable – over time. But it also may be viewed from a perspective linked more closely to current preoccupation with societal challenges such as climate change and the UN Sustainable Development Goals in general. Big data and its associated processing intensity is known to be a source of potential problems in this regard.

A fertile ground for seeking progress in this area is presented by the processing of graph structures, which have become a data representation of choice for many important analytics applications (including those related to the Sustainable Development Goals mentioned above). The efficient processing of massive graphs, as measured by appropriate metrics, can make a concrete contribution to sustainability goals.

Such metrics can include “volume” (for the size of graphs), “velocity” (for dealing also with dynamically changing topologies), and a novel metric, defined explicitly to measure capability of sustainable processing at scale, known as “viridescence”. These can help not only to construct effective graph processing optimizers, but also graph processing “greenifiers”, with an eye toward reducing the harmful effects of the underlying computing activities.

During the session...

Session Agenda

- Extreme and Sustainable Graph Processing for Urgent Challenges in Europe – **1. Radu Prodan**, University of Klagenfurt
- Commonalities, Themes and Take-Home Messages – **2. David Wallom**, University of Oxford

Final Discussion

A pair of major themes emerged from the final discussion of the workshop among all participants, with implications for the way forward in software engineering. These themes were characterized by their appearance transversally across all of the sessions.

The first theme concerned **uncertainty about the true applications** of the new technologies. Almost without exception, in each of the sessions the participants observed significant levels of uncertainty about where the new, cutting-edge technologies will find their true use cases, even after a number of years of research and development. This was especially emphasized in the quantum software engineering session; but it was also highlighted in the sessions on artificial intelligence and cybersecurity technologies (as well as noting that sustainable software engineering is a very new area in any case). This observation has also been made in other new fields such as blockchain and distributed ledger technologies. A challenge going forward will be to teach students in software engineering to be able to seek out and recognize the appropriate applications for the new technologies they are being taught.

The second theme emerged early in the session on AI, where two very siloed communities in software engineering and machine learning were described, with the attendant difficulties and failures in collaboration. The theme emerged again in the quantum session, where the difficulty of integrating communities of researchers, physicists, and practitioners was cited, because each was concerned with its own perspective, each speaking about problems in the language of its own community. The new technologies discussed in this workshop are so advanced that they are leading to a phenomenon of deep specialization in one area to the detriment of other areas. How will integrated development approaches – DevSecOps, MLOps, QuantumOps, “EcoOps” – be possible when there is no shared base of cross-cutting expertise? This will be a challenge once again for educators, and was a motivator for the conception of the cross-fertilization workshops of SWForum.eu.

One conclusion agreed by all participants was that we have not reached “the end of software engineering” as a core discipline. We will need a full cycle of renewal and adaptation of consolidated practices going forward, to give rise to a whole new generation of software engineering paradigms, models, and best practices that will help us build the systems that will accommodate both the current technologies and those yet to come.

Resources

Explore the SWForum.eu insights and findings from

“The Way Forward: Workshop on Future Challenges in Software Engineering.”

Download the speakers' presentations on [zenodo](#)

and read the post-workshop news piece **here** to gain valuable resources to effectively address future challenges in software engineering.

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